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FLEXCoop

WP7 - System Validation and Impact Assessment

FLEXCoop

D7.7 – FLEXCoop Holistic Performance Evaluation, Impact Assessment and Cost-Benefit Analysis - Final Version

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FLEXCOOP CONSORTIUM PARTNERS

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SUITE5	SUITE5 DATA INTELLIGENCE SOLUTIONS Limited
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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report presents a performance evaluation and Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA) of the most important aspects of the services developed in the FLEXCoop project. The performance evaluation focuses on solar power forecasts, full-scale experimental tests and flexibility assessment of applying the FLEXCoop system with a simulation model. Forecasts are evaluated with a developed evaluation software, which generates evaluation reports for Photo-Voltaic (PV) systems.

The flexibility assessment and simulation analysis are based on a dynamic model of either direct electrical or heat pump heated building, which is used to quantify flexibility and economic potential – which forms the basis of benefits calculations in the CBA. The CBA presents the currently related data for the case studies in the Dutch and Spanish pilot sites as well as the Dutch and Spanish energy market sections related to each pilot site. On top of these data, we identify potential savings and costs profiles which are combined to form 32 different scenarios, used to extract insights and indications for the viability of the deployment of the FLEXCoop Solution to energy cooperatives and their members.

The economic CBA from the case studies in the Netherlands and Spain, converge in the conclusion that current cost of the Bill of Materials (BoMs) and installation and customisation services per dwelling (in conjunction with the FLEXCoop Solution pricing scheme) required to deploy the FLEXCoop Solution to the prosumers is considerably high. These costs require expected savings of more than 160€ annual savings per dwelling/prosumer and cooperatives with at least 500 members using the FLEXCoop Solution.

The number of prosumers adopting the FLEXCoop Solution per cooperative is important, as, at the moment, there is no business case for cooperatives having less than 200-250 prosumers using the solution. Lowering the initial capital costs per dwelling shows some interesting scenarios in terms of viability and should be a key focus point for the future.

There are two main developments that can remedy substantially the expected benefits for cooperatives (aggregators) and their members:

- Regulatory conformity throughout Europe, to enable the deployment of the FLEXCoop Solution in conditions where more than one optimisation strategy is concurrently exploitable.
- Development, standardisation and utilisation of common open communication and control protocol for devices and platforms/solutions to significantly lower initial capital costs per dwelling.

Regardless of specific market trends, cooperatives are encouraged to explore partnerships with Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning (HVAC) device vendors and create dedicated R&D units for data analysis, modelling of business cases and simulation execution. The key point is the data acquisition and data governance. Cooperatives would maximise benefits by deploying solutions that allows them to have full “digital sovereignty” as defined by the International Data Spaces Association (IDSA) and control over the data and, if possible, have control and ownership (exclusive or shared) of the related algorithms.

This will allow cooperatives to better monitor and understand market condition and status, evaluate business cases and outline the desired functionality. The final objective is to reach a market and ecosystem awareness level where it is easy to identify the services that can maximise profit while enforcing the necessary environmental-friendly strategies. Moreover, digital sovereignty can potentially create new business models through the commercial exploitation of anonymised usage data sets or the participation in the development of the EU's energy data spaces in the overall future energy market.

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ABBREVIATIONS

aFRR	Automatic Frequency Restoration Reserve
BoM	Bill of Materials
BSP	Balance Service Provider
CBA	Cost-Benefit Analysis
CS	Case Study
DER	Distributed Energy Resources
DHW	Domestic Hot Water
DR	Demand-Response
DSO	Distribution System Operator
EUR	Euros
FRR	Frequency Restoration Reserve
HP	Heat Pump
ICT	Information and communication technology
IDSA	International Data Spaces Association
ISP	Imbalance Settlement Period
MPC	Model Predictive Control
NWP	Numerical Weather Prediction
OMIE	Operador del Mercado Ibérico-Polo Español
OSB	Open Smart Box
PV	Photovoltaic
PTU	Programming Time Unit
REE	Red Eléctrica Española
RES	Renewable Energy System
RLS	Recursive Least Squares
RMSE	Root Mean Square Error
SoC	State of Charge
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
TSO	Transport System Operator
VRES	Variable RES

1. INTRODUCTION

This report presents the results of the FLEXCoop performance evaluation and Cost Benefit Analysis (CBA). In the first part of the report the evaluation of the performance of forecasts, full-scale experiment tests and flexibility assessment is presented, and in the second part the CBA.

The solar power forecasts developed in the project are analysed in depth with the data from 13 PV systems at the pilot sites. The data is plotted in multiple ways, such that important aspects are elucidated, and thereafter the performance is quantified with KPIs. The flexibility assessment analysis is then introduced to present a methodology for assessing flexibility and implantation of simulation models, which are used for later assessment of economic potential in the CBA for revenue calculations on the Dutch automatic Frequency Restoration Reserve (aFRR). The experimental tests carried out, were full-scale tests with aim of generating data to be used for demonstrating the developed system and assess its performance. Most tests were carried out with focus on the Dutch aFRR case, but a few tests of the Spanish self-optimisation case were also run – however less successful. The aFRR case tests had naturally both more and less successful runs.

To develop the economic CBA, we are based on the pilot sites in The Netherlands and Spain, identifying 2 case studies the first investigating benefits generated by participating in the aFRR market denoted as “Case Study1 (CS1): Participation into Balancing and Ancillary Services (aFRR Market)” and the second investigating benefits generated by increasing energy self-optimisation as “Case Study 2 (CS2): Self-optimisation”. As a first step, we analyse benefits and generate the potential different savings profiles that our analyses have identified for the two case studies. In the second step, based on the modelling established for estimating benefits, we analyse costs and generate the related different cost profiles for the two case studies. By combining savings profiles and applicable costs profiles, we create scenarios on which we extract results indicating the feasibility or not of each specific scenario. Additional analyses are performed regarding cost and benefit figures to reach a break-even time of 7 years. The economic CBA is concluded with insights on benefits of a hypothetical case study with low initial capital ICT costs per dwelling.

The report is arranged such that the next section presents the forecast evaluation reporting software and an evaluation of the solar forecasts developed in the project. An example from the PV at one FLEXCoop site and a gathered analysis of all 13 PV systems. The third section is about the flexibility assessment, where a model for a building and its heating system, with a heat pump, is defined and applied for flexibility assessment and simulation with three years of data for the Dutch climate. The fourth section is the evaluation of the full-scale experiment tests of the Dutch and Spanish scenarios. The fifth section presents the economic CBA, where results for both the Dutch and the Spanish business scenarios are presented. The sixth section presents the environmental CBA and finally, in the last section, the conclusions are drawn.

2. KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATOR EVALUATION OF THE SOLAR POWER FORECASTING SYSTEM

In this section the solar forecasting system in FLEXCoop is evaluated. We present the components which have been developed in the project. First, the solar forecast evaluation reporting tool is presented – it includes a short description of the Opens Source “R” package “onlineforecast” (partly developed in FLEXCoop, see <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/onlineforecast/onlineforecast.pdf>), which is used for calculating the forecasts. The reporting tool can generate a unified evaluation of solar forecasts for a specific photovoltaic (PV) system. Data in the form of observations of hourly (potentially other resolutions can be used) generated power and related Numerical Weather Predictions (NWP) of global radiation are given in a specified format. The output is a report in html format, which provides insights into the data quality and provides a rather detailed analysis, which will enable the reader to identify issues in data, as well as insights into forecast quality etc. The aim is that this software can be used for evaluation, both by experts to examine and evaluate observed power data, NWP and forecasts, but also for non-experts as a tool for monitoring the performance of the forecasting system for their own installations. The reporting software uses the package “onlineforecast”, which is now available for free via the CRAN, for more details on how to use the package and additional examples, see our website <http://onlineforecasting.org>.

Second, an analysis of forecasts for a single site is presented, it’s based on the output of the reporting tool, and finally a comparative analysis for all sites in the project is included.

2.1. Solar power forecast evaluation software

The format of the solar power observations and NWP must be as described in [12] for the systems for which to generate evaluation reports. Given this data, an html document is generated for each system consisting of the following subsections (as tabs):

- Solar power
- NWP
- NWP & Power
- Forecasts
- Score

In the following sections the analysis under each tab is described. In the reports short and concise instructions are provided for each presented result.

The forecast models and score KPIs are presented in [12] and [1] , respectively. The applied KPIs are the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), which measures the quality of the solar power forecast in terms of predicting the mean power, defined as “SYR 1” in the FLEXCoop PMV (D2.5). And the completeness, which measures the ability not to have gaps in the forecasts (especially important in auto-regressive models), defined as “SYR 2”. With regards to the models, the only not presented model is the adaptive diurnal mean, which is an “advanced” reference model, representing the “best model without NWP”. This model is based on a diurnal curve formed by a mean and Fourier series as input:

$$Y_{t+k|t} = \beta_{0,t+k|t} + \beta_{1,t+k|t} f_{fs}(u_t; n_{har}) + \varepsilon_{t+k|t}$$

Where t denotes the time in hours, k denotes the horizon in hourly steps, Y is the output, $f_{fs}()$ generates the harmonic series as described in [12], u_t is the time of day, n_{har} is the number of harmonics and the epsilon denotes the error. This model will fit a diurnal mean as a function of the time of day, hence catching the pattern of the mean of the solar power. It is fitted using the adaptive Recursive Least Squares RLS (see [12]) scheme, hence adapts to the changes over time.

2.1.1. Solar power

The observed solar power data is analysed by the following plots and KPIs:

- **“Plot observations”**: An overview of the full series and missing values
- **“Plot of completeness for time of day”**: Examine potential patterns in the missing values
- **“Box plots of power for time of day”**: Examine patterns in the of solar power
- **“Plot of power over shorter period”**: See in details the observations in a shorter period

2.1.2. NWP

The global radiation NWPs provided as input for the solar forecasts are analysed by the following plots and KPIs:

- **“Plot of global radiation NWPs for all included horizons”**: An overview of NWP forecast series for all horizons (lead times) and missing values
- **“Plot of NWP completeness vs. horizon”**: To examine potential patterns in the missing values
- **“Box plots of selected horizons NWPs”**: Examine patterns in the NWPs
- **“Pairs plot of selected horizons NWPs”**: To examine the relation between different (selected) horizons of the NWPs
- **“Zoom period of selected horizons NWPs”**: See details in the NWPs in a shorter period

2.1.3. NWP & Power

The relations between the solar power observations and the global radiation NWPs are analysed by the following plots and KPIs:

- **“Plots of power and all NWPs”**: An overview of the NWPs and the solar power
- **“Plots of scatter between power and lagged selected horizons NWPs”**: Examine the relation between the observations and NWPs, with different lagging included to investigate potential synchronisation issues
- **“Plots of power and selected horizons NWPs”**: See details in a shorter period

2.1.4. Forecasts

The forecast model implemented in FLEXCoop is applied with the NWP as input, alongside with the adaptive diurnal mean reference model. The resulting solar power forecasts from the models are analysed by the following plots and KPIs:

- **“Plot of all predictions for model with NWP input”**: An overview of the solar power forecasts from the NWP input model
- **“Plot of zoom period of predictions for model with NWP input for selected horizons NWP”**: A zoom of forecasts for selected forecast horizons from the NWP input model
- **“Plot of all predictions for adaptive diurnal mean model”**: An overview of the solar power forecasts from the reference model with the adaptive diurnal mean model
- **“Plot of zoom period of predictions for adaptive diurnal mean model”**: A zoom of forecasts for selected forecast horizons from the with the adaptive diurnal mean model

2.1.5. Score

The final analysis part is of the forecast performance, where the NWP input model forecast performance is compared to three reference models:

- Diurnal adaptive mean model: The model described above
- Diurnal persistence: The latest available observation with a lag of a whole days matching the time of day of the forecast, is used as the forecast
- Diurnal mean model: A non-adaptive version of the diurnal mean model, simply the average of all power at each time of day

The forecast performance is summarized by the following plots and KPIs:

- **“RMSE vs. horizon”**: The RMSE as a function of the horizon is plotted for each of the four models
- **“Completeness vs. horizon”**: The completeness as a function of horizon, which indicates how missing values in the forecasts depends on the horizon

2.2. Case study for a FLEXCoop single PV system

In this section, an example of a case study based on data from a single FLEXCoop user with a PV system is presented. This section is updated from D7.5, since much data has been collected since April 2020. We now present the evaluation report from User FL3S which had reliable data with few gaps. The user is located in Spain.

We step through the analysis of different features: First the observed solar power series (in W), then the NWP (W/m²), then both together, and finally the solar power forecasts.

2.2.1. Solar power

First the overview plot of the entire series of hourly solar power observations from the PV system of the user is shown below in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Hourly solar power from the user’s PV (W), missing values are indicated in the lower plot

The series cover the period from 2020-04-23 to 2020-11-15, during the period only few observations are missing.

The box-plots of the power vs. time of day can be seen in Figure 2 below.

Figure 2. Solar power (W) distribution during the day compared with sun elevation (normed to range 0 to max (solar power)).

The plots reveal that the PV system generates most power during the midday, hence it’s pointing towards south. Further, some high values are seen at night, they must be considered simply as “wrong” values.

2.2.2. NWP

Box-plots of the Global radiation NWP's shown in Figure 3 below reveal that the patterns are, as they should be (depending on how tilted the panel was), similar to the sun elevation (note that k denotes the forecast horizon in hourly steps, i.e. k_{24} is a plot of the forecast for 24 hours ahead).

Figure 3. Sun elevation in the upper left plot (normed to range 0 to max(NWP's)) distribution during the day compared with NWP's (W/m^2).

2.3. NWP & Power

A zoom on a shorter period is plotted in Figure 4 below (note again that k denotes the forecast horizon in hourly steps, i.e. $I_{k_{24}}$ is the forecast for 24 hours ahead). This plot can be used to visually inspect forecasts to find any obvious improper patterns (e.g. lags).

Figure 4. Short period solar power (W) and NWP (W/m²).

We can see that for most of the time, the power and the NWP follow each other pretty well, e.g. the two days, 12th and 13th, both have a slightly lower level.

2.3.1. Forecasts

In the plot for a shorter period, we see the solar power forecasts in the middle plot in Figure 5 below.

Figure 5. Upper plot is of the solar power (W), middle plot is of the solar power forecasts (W) with the power indicated by the green line, and lower plot is of the NWP (W/m²).

It’s clear from this, that the model uses the NWP’s, however it’s also clear that when there is an error in the NWP’s, it’s of course passed directly through to the solar power forecasts, e.g. seen the 12’t, where the NWP’s predicts too low radiation, hence the prediction also becomes too low for the solar power.

2.3.2. Score

The RMSE as a function of the horizon is plotted in Figure 6 below for the 6 models fitted.

Figure 6. RMSE as a function of the horizon (W).

It can be seen that there’s an improvement from the simple reference models (Diurnal persistence and Diurnal mean model) to the adaptive model (Diurnal mean adaptive), which doesn’t use the NWP’s, is quite significant. The NWP models improves from there, especially on the shorter horizons, thus indicating that they do provide additional information, however it’s not a big leap forward, and on longer horizons this improvement is marginal.

2.4. Analysis of power forecasts for all PV systems

In this section an analysis of the forecasts for all the PV systems at FLEXCoop pilot sites is presented. We have made a reporting software for getting an overview of forecasts for all systems, similar to the described reporting software for a single PV. An overview report has been generated and the results from the overview report are presented in this section.

2.4.1. Solar power

To get an overview of the observed power some key figures are listed in Table 1. With summaries of non-available values in the solar data. The columns are: “nOutliers (%)” is the proportion of observations classified as outlier values, “nNodiffs (%)” is the proportion of observations which are constant between two samples, “nNAs (%)” is the proportion of not available (NA) (ie. missing) values, “nNonNas” is the proportion of available values and finally, “nObservations” is the number of observations.

Table 1. With summaries of non-available values in the solar data. The columns are: “nOutliers (%)” is the proportion of observations classified as outlier values, “nNodiffs

(%)” is the proportion of observations which are constant between two samples, “nNAs (%)” is the proportion of not available (NA) (ie. missing) values, “nNonNas” is the proportion of available values and finally, “nObservations” is the number of observations.

	nOutliers (%)	nNodiffs (%)	nNAs (%)	nNonNAs (%)	nObservations
UserFL5NL	0	0	46.47	53.53	4943
UserFL12NL	2.7	0	31.41	68.59	4922
UserFL13NL	0	0	13.23	86.77	4943
UserFL20NL	0	0	45.72	54.28	4943
UserFL21NL	0	0	14.48	85.52	2652
UserFL22NL	0	0	48.49	51.51	4943
UserFL23NL	0	0	44.89	55.11	4925
UserReneHome	0	0	52.95	47.05	4925
UserFL1S	0	0	39.39	60.61	4943
UserFL2S	0	0	40.17	59.83	4922
UserFL3S	0	0	6.4	93.6	4925
UserFL5S	1.44	0	83.11	16.89	4943
UserFL28S	0	0	10.62	89.38	3974

It’s seen that we have 13 PV systems included: 8 in Netherlands and 5 in Spain. The first two columns list the proportion, which has been removed as outliers – only two systems have outliers removed. The “nNA (%)” column is the proportion of observations which are NA values, and for most of the systems, it’s quite a lot, unfortunately. Finally, it can be seen that the number of observations corresponds to a period around 200 days for most systems (hourly data).

To get further insight into where the observations are missing, the plot in Figure 7 is presented. It plots the completeness (proportion of available values) as a function of time of day, for each system.

Figure 7. Plots of the completeness (proportion of available values) vs. time of day for each system.

As seen from the curves, quite a few of the Dutch systems have almost no night values available, which is a bit strange, but doesn’t really matter, since they are anyway not included in the

forecast scoring. However, it’s more an issue that many of the systems have missing values during the day. The reason for this is not known, it might be due to network communication issues where data is lost.

In the Figure 8 below, the minimum, median and maximum value, as a function of time of day, is plotted for each system.

Figure 8. Plots of the minimum, median and maximum value, as a function of time of day for each system.

A clear difference in size of the systems can be seen, with one system (FL13NL) being very big, and the remaining being still well sized systems for regular sized family buildings.

2.5. NWP

The Numerical Weather Predictions used are obtained from [26]. They are extracted for the locations of the systems and cover the same period as the power observations. The plot in Figure 9 below is of completeness vs. Horizon.

Figure 9. Plots of the completeness vs. the horizon for the generated solar power forecasts.

It is clear that there is a systematic pattern, as more values are missing for shorter horizons, it can be due to issues related to when the NWP’s are extracted.

2.6. Forecasts

Finally, the scores for the forecast models are evaluated for each system each of the systems. First the overview of how many observations were included in the forecast score calculation is given in Table 2 below.

Table 2. Summary of the included observations in the score calculations.

	UserFL5NL	UserFL12NL	UserFL13NL	UserFL20NL	UserFL21NL	UserFL22NL	UserFL23NL
n in score	1568.00	970.00	2076	1450.00	698.00	914.00	1671.00
Proportion of all (%)	31.72	19.71	42	29.33	26.32	18.49	33.93
Number of obs	4943.00	4922.00	4943	4943.00	2652.00	4943.00	4925.00
	UserReneHome	UserFL1S	UserFL2S	UserFL3S	UserFL5S	UserFL28S	
n in score	1272.00	1067.00	1251.00	2202.00	107.00	1409.00	
Proportion of all (%)	25.83	21.59	25.42	44.71	2.16	35.46	
Number of obs	4925.00	4943.00	4922.00	4925.00	4943.00	3974.00	

Notice, that night values were removed, but even so, we still include at least 698 observations in the score calculations (for each horizon) for each system.

The improvements in two stages are plotted in Figure 10 in order to compare the models: from the diurnal persistence reference model (simplest model) to the adaptive diurnal mean (not using NWP’s) to the model with both a diurnal and NWP’s. A positive improve indicates that the latter model is more accurate.

Figure 10. Improvements in RMSE for each system in two stages:

In the upper plot of Figure 10 the improvement from the diurnal reference model to the adaptive diurnal mean without NWP input. In the lower plot of Figure 10 the improvement from the adaptive diurnal mean model without NWP input to the similar with NWP input.

It can be seen that in all cases there are quite significant improvements from the reference model to the adaptive diurnal model. This indicates that the adaptive forecast models can estimate the conditional mean efficiently. In the second stage it is seen, that for approximately half the systems improvements are obtained using the NWP. There seems to be a tendency, that NWP improve the forecasts for the Spanish, opposed to the Dutch, systems. A possible explanation can be, that the NWP are obtained from [26] meteorological service, which run more detailed models for Spain than for Netherlands.

Finally, the RMSE and NRMSE scores as a function of the horizon for the best model fitted for each system are shown in the plots in Figure 11 below. The normalized values are relative to the maximum observed value for each system.

Figure 11. The upper plot is of the RMSE and the lower is of the NRMSE scores as a function of the horizons for the best model fitted for each system.

It's found that a normalized forecast error in the range of 10% to 20% is quite satisfactorily. There are some unexpected patterns, e.g. for UserFL5S, which is also one of the systems with most missing values, in particular in the day time hours. Regarding the use of the NWP's is the best for most of the systems – it would be very interesting to research further into which NWP's are optimal to use for solar power forecasting.

2.7. Conclusions

The solar forecast performance evaluation software presented in [3] has been used to analyse the final data set from the project. In [3] not much data was available, but in the final data set we have around 200 days of data for 13 systems – some missing data though. However enough to carry out a thorough evaluation of the solar forecast models developed and applied in the project.

First, a case study for a single system was presented. A system with the most complete data was chosen and highlights from the evaluation report was picked out to illustrate the most important features of the forecasts. The results indicate, that for the particular PV system the developed forecast models have a satisfactory improvement over the diurnal persistence reference model, and also an improvement when using the NWP's as input – however it's not a real leap in performance. As also illustrated, the NWP errors pass through to the solar power forecasts and thus it leads to the conclusion, that the models do make use of the NWP's, and that in order to

achieve further improvements different NWP or potentially combination of different NWP should be used.

Finally, the forecasts calculated for all 13 systems were evaluated. Albeit quite a big fraction of missing values for some of the systems, we do have enough data to give a profound judgement of the forecast quality. The general conclusion is, that the models work quite robustly and deliver a satisfactory forecast quality for many applications, with a level of error between 10% to 20% NRMSE (normalized with the max observed power). Most of the best sites had a best selected model with NWP input, with a tendency of this for the Spanish sites – where also better NWP were available, opposed to the Dutch sites. Hence, again, further improvements can be achieved with better NWP as input to the models.

3. FLEXIBILITY ASSESSMENT

In this section it is presented how the flexibility assessment is carried out. The approach is based on a model of the heat dynamics of a building and its heating system. The model can be fitted to data from experiments, and different flexibility KPIs can be calculated. First the model is presented, then the flexibility assessment is outlined, followed by examples of model simulation.

3.1. Model

A state-space model of coupled differential equations is set up for predicting the heat consumption and indoor room temperature of a building, as a function of the ambient temperature and global radiation.

The model used for modelling the heating system and the building consists of the following system equations. The heating system (e.g. radiators or underfloor) is modelled with a simple finite-element model, where first set of states of the model represent temperatures of the outlet (return) of each compartment

$$\begin{aligned} dT_{\text{ret}1} &= \frac{n_c}{C_h} \left((T_{\text{for}} - T_{\text{ret}1}) f(T_{\text{set}}, T_i) + \frac{1}{R_{\text{ih}} n_c} (T_i - T_{\text{ret}1}) + g_A \Phi_s \right) dt \\ dT_{\text{ret}2} &= \frac{n_c}{C_h} \left((T_{\text{ret}1} - T_{\text{ret}2}) f(T_{\text{set}}, T_i) + \frac{1}{R_{\text{ih}} n_c} (T_i - T_{\text{ret}2}) \right) dt \\ &\vdots \\ dT_{\text{ret}} &= \frac{n_c}{C_h} \left((T_{\text{ret}n_c-1} - T_{\text{ret}}) f(T_{\text{set}}, T_i) + \frac{1}{R_{\text{ih}} n_c} (T_i - T_{\text{ret}n_c}) \right) dt \end{aligned}$$

The compartment temperatures are thus simply the (return) temperature of each compartment. The number of compartments in the applied model is $n_c = 3$.

The interior temperature state is:

$$dT_i = \frac{1}{C_i} \left(\frac{1}{R_{\text{ih}} n_c} (T_i - T_{\text{ret}1}) + \frac{1}{R_{\text{ih}} n_c} (T_i - T_{\text{ret}2}) + \dots + \frac{1}{R_{\text{ih}} n_c} (T_i - T_{\text{ret}n_c}) + \frac{1}{R_{\text{ie}}} (T_e - T_i) \right) dt$$

The input variables are:

- T_{for} : The forward temperature (set according to a heat curve as explained below) in °C
- T_e : The external air temperature (ambient temperature) in °C
- Φ_s : The solar radiation (global radiation) in W/m². It can be seen that the solar radiation enters into the heating system, in the case of floor heating this is natural, however with radiators this is quite a model simplification

The parameters will be presented below.

The following are the measurement equations (subscripts are left out). The heating power:

$$\Phi_k^h = (T_{\text{for}} - T_{\text{ret}}) f(T_{\text{set}}, T_i)$$

The return temperature:

$$T_k^{\text{ret}} = T_{\text{ret}}$$

The interior temperature:

$$T_k^{\text{i}} = T_{\text{i}}$$

The thermostatic control which keeps the indoor temperature stable is:

$$f(T_{\text{set}}, T_{\text{i}}) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-\alpha(T_{\text{set}} - T_{\text{i}})}} c_w Q_{\text{max}}$$

The thermostatic control is illustrated below:

Figure 12. Sigmoid functions for modelling proportional control

The heat curve controlling the forward temperature (T_{for}) as a function of the external temperature is:

$$T_{\text{for}}(T_e) = 25 + b_1(20 - T_e)$$

where $b_1 = 0.8$ is used.

The COP of the heat pump as a function of the forward temperature is:

$$\text{cop}(T_{\text{for}}) = 0.4 \frac{1 - (7 + 273.15)^{-1}}{T_{\text{for}} + 273.15}$$

Thus, it is assuming a 7 °C cold reservoir temperature (the usual assumption of average ground temperature in Northern Europe, so valid for the Dutch case) and an efficiency of 0.4. An illustration of the heat curve and the cop is plotted below:

Figure 13. Heating curve and COP used in the model

The parameter values used in the present simulations are:

- $R_{ih} = 0.1 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}/\text{kW}$ is the thermal resistance between the floor heating and the internal
- $R_{ie} = 3 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}/\text{kW}$ is the thermal resistance between internal and external, hence the parameter determining the insulation level of the building
- $C_i = 4 \text{ kWh}/^\circ\text{C}$ is the effective heat capacity of the internal
- $C_h = 3 \text{ kWh}/^\circ\text{C}$ is the effective heat capacity of the floor
- $g_A = 5 \text{ m}^2$ is the effective transparency of windows
- $Q_{\max} = 400 \text{ l/h}$, is the flow of water in the heating pipes
- $c_w = 0.00118 \text{ kWh}/\text{kg } ^\circ\text{C}$, is the specific heat capacity of water
- $\alpha = 3$, sets slope in the control function, see plots above

These R and C values are taken as reasonable values for a standard insulated building with floor heating according to a standard single-family building. This will be further developed in the final version, where a range of parameters for representative buildings will be examined, such that they are adjusted to reflect a wider range of buildings and can also be estimated based on observed data using methods like [13].

3.2. Flexibility

Several suggestions for characterizing and measuring the flexibility have been suggested in the literature, see [14], [15], [16] and [17]. Some methodologies include the temperature bounds in the flexibility measurement, thus making the result very particular (i.e. includes the current inhabitants' preferences and behaviour), others do not. The key to flexibility assessment is to be able to setup a model, similar to the presented model above, of the heat dynamics predicting the load and temperature. Potentially the parameters of the model can be estimated using data from a test. With the model (which naturally has been a dynamic model) the flexibility can be characterized and measured.

With the model the two important signals must be described:

- Electrical load. The model must be able to predict the load, since this load must be shifted around to meet the needs of the grid.
- Internal air temperature. The model must predict the internal air temperature in order to learn the flexibility boundaries.

The model can be of varying complexity ranging from: the simplest, which can predict only the time it takes for the temperature to drop to a minimum temperature level [16][18], and to a very complex model, with which the full response to control variables can be predicted. Further, some methodologies include an optimisation according to some given penalty signal [14].

The flexibility KPIs: saturation time and saturation curve, presented below are directly inspired by [14], [18] and [19].

First, the saturation time is defined as the time for the interval temperature to reach the lower temperature bound from the base line temperature which, of course, is a function of the inputs: external temperature and solar radiation.

The model is applied to simulate at different external temperature levels (T_e), with zero solar radiation, the internal temperature decay from the base line temperature ($21\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) and the time to reach the lower temperature limit can be calculated, as illustrated:

Figure 14. Saturation time illustrated

The saturation time is plotted as a function of the external temperature, thus forming the saturation curve:

Figure 15. Saturation curve

It is seen that at $-5\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ external temperature the saturation time is around 1.5 hours and for $15\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ it is 8.5 hours. This curve provides a very simple KPI of flexibility, which can be calculated

with an arbitrarily complicated model, and can be used to give a very simple comparison of flexibility between buildings.

A similar power increase KPI can be defined, but we will not go further with this, since we will rather turn to applying the model for assessing revenue in the coming sections.

3.3. Simulations

In this section, the presented model is used for simulating load and temperatures through a period of 3 years in the Netherlands. These simulations will later be used for analysing the revenue potential in the Dutch business scenario. The simulation results presented here are just for verification of the model, which is run for the entire 3-year period to check that no unexpected behaviour is found for the entire period.

3.3.1. Climate data for the Netherlands

As meteorological input data for the simulations the “meteo - surface observations of common atmospheric variables at 10 minute interval at Cabauw” is downloaded from Koninklijk Nederlands Meteorologisch Instituut ([20]). The data consists of time series of usual met. variable with 10 min. sampling period. Data from 2017-01-01 to 2020-02-08 is used. The data consists of time series of usual met. variable with 10 min. sampling period. Data from 2017-01-01 to 2020-02-08 is used.

3.3.2. Heat and temperatures

The heating and room temperatures from simulations at three different room temperature set points. The baseline temperature is 21 °C, and the lower is 19 °C and the upper is 23 °C.

The results of the simulations for the entire period are shown in the figure below. The upper plot is the heating power for the three room temperature set point levels: Ph19, Ph21 and Ph23. The mid plot is of the room temperatures in the three scenarios, and the lower plot is meteorological inputs: T_e is the external temperature and P_s is the global radiation:

Figure 16. Whole period simulation: Heating, Indoor temperature and met. inputs

It is seen how the temperatures are kept stable in the winter, where the building is heated. In the summer period, the temperatures go very high sometimes, which is not realistic in an occupied building, since in reality there will be ventilation, which is not modelled, e.g. window openings. However, since only the heating period is used in the revenue calculations in the CBA, the summer period will not influence the results.

It can be seen that the heating level is highest in the winter period, thus this is where most flexibility can be delivered, whereas in the summer period the heating is turned off (between 15. May and 15. Sep.) and no flexibility can be delivered there.

A plot similar to the previous is shown for a week in the winter. It shows how the solar radiation increases the room temperature, which causes the heating to reduce keeping the room temperature quite stable:

Figure 17. Winter period: Heating, Indoor temperature and met. inputs

A plot similar to the previous is shown for a week in the spring. It is seen how the high level of solar radiation heats up the building during the day, such that only during the night the heating is active:

Figure 18. Spring period: heating, indoor temperature and met. inputs

3.4. Conclusions

We have presented a model, which can be applied for simulating power and temperatures in a building heated with a heat pump with thermostatic control. It can be used to calculate flexibility measures and it is demonstrated how the two flexibility KPIs: saturation time and saturation time curve are calculated. Finally, the model is applied to simulate a 3 years period of 10-minute values in three scenarios: A baseline with 21 °C. and a low power 19 °C and high power 23 °C. One important point to be made from this is that the flexibility potential heavily relies on the climatic conditions, in a way which is conceptually intuitive, but not straight forward to grasp. Considering the level of flexibility available one has to distinguish between *up-regulation (lowering demand)* and *down-regulation (increasing demand)*. From the saturation curve, only presented for up-regulation, it is clear that *temporally* most flexibility is available in warm weather (the heating can be shut off for a longer time before the lower temperature limit is reached), however the flexibility in terms of *power level* is higher in the winter, since more power is used for heating and thus more power can be lowered. In warm periods little or no up-regulation is available. For *down-regulation* the relation is opposite and it must be taken into account that in warm periods there is no flexibility available at all, since there is no need for heating. Therefore, studies of flexibility should encompass the surrounding energy system needs, as in presented below in the CBA, where the model is used for simulating deliverance of flexibility to the Dutch aFRR market.

4. TEST EVALUATION

The FLEXCoop system ability to function as designed in the two business cases has been tested in a series of test experiments. The first tests were carried out in the Hypertech labs in summer

2020 in order to test the system components and integration. Then, after developments based on the learnings from the lab tests, the tests were shifted to pilot sites, mainly at the friendly user FL1S, however the conditions were still too warm to get useful results. As the weather got colder during November, we could start training the flexibility models and carry out the final tests.

During the project we developed a short automatic reporting, which summarized the results of each test for each prosumer. These worked well during the testing phase, allowing all project partners to see the results of each test rather quickly, and the cause of problems which needed to be fixed could be decided iteratively in common regular meetings. Testing such systems, which are composed of many components working together to control systems at remote pilot sites, is not an easy task – many things can go wrong. The series of tests carried out is presented in Table 3, each test lasted one day.

Table 3. Overview of the tests carried out at the pilot sites.

User	Type of test	Notes categories	Notes (i.e. when the system was switched off)
FL1S			
2020-10-27	aFRR	Extra info	from 10:00 to 14h --> 4h test. test ended well
2020-11-03	aFRR	Stop cause	Started at 00:00 and stopped at 03:50 for too high temperature
2020-11-17	aFRR	Stop cause	Started at 08.00 and stopped at 17:00 for too high temperature
2020-11-19	self-optimisation	Stop cause	Started at 08.00 and stopped at 11:20 for too high temperature
2020-11-24	self-optimisation	Stop cause	Started at 08:00 and stopped at 12:20 for too high temperature
2020-11-26	aFRR	Stop cause	Started at 08:00 and stopped at 13:30 for too low temperature
2020-12-01	self-optimisation	Extra info	No logs on stop time
2020-12-03	aFRR	Extra info	No problems during the test
2020-12-09	self-optimisation	Extra info	Starting at 10:00 and ending at 20:00 without any problem
2020-12-10	self-optimisation	Stop cause	Started at 08:00 and stopped at 12:30 for too high temperature
2020-12-14	self-optimisation	Stop cause	Starting at 11:00 stopped at 13:45 for too high temperature
2020-12-15	aFRR	No notes	
2020-12-17	aFRR	Stop cause	Down regulation (consume more) the first ISP, which lead to exceeding upper comfort bound. The user switched of Wifi from 01:00 to 09:00. Test restarted at 15 local time
FL2S			
2020-12-14	self-optimisation	Extra info	Starting at 09:00 and ending without user complain at 20:00. Second source of heating on the house
2020-12-15	aFRR	Extra info	Second source of heating on the house
2020-12-17	aFRR	Extra info	Second source of heating on the house
FL7S			
2020-12-03	aFRR	No notes	
2020-12-17	aFRR	No notes	
FL16S			
2020-12-15	aFRR	Extra info	Power clamp measures other load than HVAC also, further, there seems to be other heating sources

FL17S			
2020-12-15	aFRR	No notes	
2020-12-17	aFRR	Stop cause	OSB offline at least from 13:05 to 16:00. OSB was unplugged. The user plugs it back at 16:05
FL27S			
2020-11-26	aFRR	Stop cause	Approx. 12:30 by misunderstanding from the user (not due to discomfort)
2020-12-03	aFRR	No notes	
2020-12-17	aFRR	Stop cause	A healing process of the OSB occurred at 16:00 local time, which led to not receiving signals until midmorning when Hypertech restarted the test.

From the table it can be seen, from the notes in the right column, that there were many issues (which is not strange) which came up during testing, however after the initial tests quite a few tests were carried out successfully. The two business cases were tested: The aFRR (Dutch) and the self-optimisation (Spanish). It can be seen that the tests in the beginning were focused on the FL1S user. In those tests when following the reference load (baseload+delivered up/down power) the temperature increased too much and the user stopped the test. The main reason was simply that the outdoor conditions were too warm such that no heating actually was required – leading to little information for training a good model, as well as when the heat was turned up it quickly got too warm inside. It improved as more data was gathered during the tests and finally at the end of November the conditions were cold enough to get really useful tests (full day operation of the heat pump). From there on other pilot sites were included in the tests.

In the following sections an evaluation of the tests is presented: first for the aFRR and second for the self-optimisation tests.

4.1. aFRR tests

As described in [1] Section 3 the aFRR case is focused on the participation in balancing markets where up and down regulating power is delivered. To understand how the conditions of actual operation is, we have carried out an analysis with the aim of characterizing the aFRR market activations. It is presented first and thereafter the evaluation of the test results are presented.

4.1.1. aFRR test design

In order to learn how the conditions when delivering regulating power is, a characterisation of the activations at the Dutch aFRR market [21] was carried out. Notice, that the smallest possible bid to the market is 1 MW and from there in steps of 1 MW.

Data was downloaded from [21] and processed into four signals:

- The proportion of activated 1 minute intervals in the 15 minutes PTU (programming time unit, simply the time interval) with *up regulation* activation levels equal or above 1 MW
- The proportion of activated 1 minute intervals in the 15 minutes PTU with *up regulation* activation levels equal or above 10 MW

- The proportion of activated 1 minute intervals in the 15 minutes PTU with *down regulation* activation levels equal or above 1 MW
- The proportion of activated 1 minute intervals in the 15 minutes PTU with *down regulation* activation levels equal or above 10 MW

These signals represent the power that would have been activated if bids had been submitted with the most advantageous price for the market (lowest price for up regulation and highest price for down regulation). The data covers 2 years from 2018-03-01 to 2020-03-01.

Daily averages of the proportion of activated slots are plotted in Figure 19 over the period.

Figure 19. Daily averages of the proportion of activation for up regulation and down regulation.

It can be seen that all days have some activation in both directions and that there seems to be a slight seasonal variation with a lower level in the summer for the down regulation levels.

A five days period are plotted of 15 minute proportions in Figure 20.

Figure 20. A five days period of proportion of activation where the level is at least 1 MW. Plot of 15 minutes values.

It can be seen that almost all the time either up or down regulation is activated, primarily in one direction at a time.

The activated proportion for the 10 MW activation level is plotted in Figure 21.

Figure 21. A five days period of proportion of activation where the level is at least 10 MW. Plot of 15 minutes average values.

It can be seen that the pattern is almost the same as for 1 MW, only slightly lower, hence most of the time more than 10 MW are activated.

Finally, the distribution of the length of the activation periods are calculated and showed as histograms in Figure 22. Histograms of the lengths of activation periods in PTUs (i.e. 15 minutes slots on the x-axis). A period is defined as the time from activation in one-direction, till the activation becomes zero again..

Figure 22. Histograms of the lengths of activation periods in PTUs (i.e. 15 minutes slots on the x-axis). A period is defined as the time from activation in one-direction, till the activation becomes zero again.

Obviously, one can see that there most periods have a length shorter than 1 hour. The distribution has the shape of an exponential distribution. The similar histogram for 10 MW level is not included here, but we can report that period lengths distribution has a very similar shape.

From this short analysis of activations on the Dutch aFRR it has been found that the activation period lengths distribution is exponential shaped and thus it should be considered to use test signals with the same properties in terms of duration and mutual exclusive up- and down-regulation activations.

4.1.2. Generation of activation test sequences

In this section considerations carried out in the design of experiments for the aFRR case are presented – it is noted that due to delays pushing the testing to a rather short period at the end of the project, the test sequences used were simpler . However, we find it valuable to include the test design considerations here for others to benefit from it.

In order to be able to evaluate the relation between forecast accuracy and other variables, it's important that the activations are independent of other variables (e.g. time, weather, building use) and thus the activations must randomized. The following should be randomized within operational ranges of the activations in the particular setup:

- Time
- Duration
- Direction

Several methods for randomisation schemes are suggested in system identification literature. The pseudo-random binary sequences (PRBS) are a popular choice as they are optimal in several ways, at least for experiments design for identification of linear time invariant systems [28].

4.1.2.1. PRBS

A PRBS can be generated as described in [25]. First a value n is set between 2 and 11, defining the maximum length of being in each state, and then a seed is set.

Below in Figure 23 is an example with $n=5$.

Figure 23. A PRBS signal generated with the maximum step length in either state is $n=5$.

The quality of this signal is that the auto-correlation function (ACF) is similar to white noise, hence there is no auto-correlation (“internal” correlation) in the series, as well as, since the PRBS has no periodicities, there is no cross-correlation to other signals. Finally, the period lengths are exponentially distributed as seen below in Figure 24.

Figure 24. Histogram showing the distribution of the lengths of the periods in the PRBS signal with $n=5$.

4.1.2.2. Blended PRBS

One approach to make both up and down activation in the same period, is to blend a positive and negative PRBS by splitting in the periods and them randomly blending them (i.e. drawing selecting the order of the -1,0,1 periods). This of course depends on a pseudo-random sequence, however by setting a seed and sharing the code, the particular series can easily be replicated by

others. The series plotted in Figure 25 below is obtained by blending the previously generated PRBS.

Figure 25. The randomly blended PRBS.

The blended sequence exhibits a slight increase in ACF, but an insignificant cross-correlation to ambient air temperature (downloaded from the Dutch weather service), as seen in Figure 26 below.

Figure 26. ACF and CCF of the blended PRBS. The CCF is to ambient temperature of a randomly selected period.

The sequences can be modified in many ways; however, it must be understood how the manipulations affect correlation patterns.

4.1.3. Test results

Data were recorded during each test - relevant subsets are used here for the evaluation.

The KPIs described in D7.2 will here be used for evaluation. Firstly, the predicted up- and down-regulating power is analysed and, secondly, the baseline forecasts are evaluated.

4.1.3.1. Delivered up and down regulating power

First an overview will be given where the KPIs are presented in tables for each test and each user. Thereafter in the following section the data from selected tests will be analysed to point out useful learnings of what went well and what went worse.

To refresh the aFRR setup and the KPIs: At 14 the day before operation the baseline load is predicted and reported - it’s the power to be consumed during the day in 15 minute slots. Furthermore, the up- and down-regulation flexibility (possible potential deviation from the baseline in each direction without compromising the user comfort) is calculated and reported. During the day the aggregator can request activation of the reported flexibility in each slot.

The results of delivering up-regulation power (decreased consumption) are presented in the Table 4. The upper table shows the total requested up-regulation in kWh. The lower table shows the proportion (in %) of this requested regulation, which was actually delivered regulation (i.e. the actual deviation from the baseline summed through the 15 min. time slots).. Note that the values are energy, not power, since it’s the delivered power integrated over time (here just summed through the 15 min. time slots of the day).

Table 4. The upper table shows the total requested up-regulation in kWh. The lower table shows the proportion (in %) of this requested regulation, which was actually delivered regulation (i.e. the actual deviation from the baseline summed through the 15 min. time slots).

	2020-11-26	2020-12-03	2020-12-15	2020-12-17
FL16S			0.49	
FL17S			5.52	6.38
FL1S	1.73	0.86	0.86	4.32
FL27S	2.12	1.49		3.82
FL2S			0.31	0.94
FL7S		6.54		6.54

	2020-11-26	2020-12-03	2020-12-15	2020-12-17
FL16S			26	
FL17S			93	0
FL1S	98	100	100	100
FL27S	100	31		30
FL2S			0	0
FL7S		99		100

From the requested up-regulation values it can be seen that the level was quite varying between the tests and between the prosumers. This is because of several reasons: different size of the Heat Pump (HP) systems, different calculated flexibility and the aggregator activated different proportions of the available flexibility.

From the delivered proportions it can be seen that there are really differences in the performance. For example, FL1S, where quite a few tests were run in advance of the final tests, manage to deliver nearly all the requested regulation, whereas FL2S didn’t really deliver anything. In the following section we will enlighten what caused these differences with a more detailed analysis.

The similar values for the down-regulation (consume more) are presented in the Table 5. The upper table shows the total requested up-regulation in kWh. The lower table shows the proportion (in %) of this requested regulation, which was actually delivered regulation (i.e. the actual deviation from the baseline summed through the 15 min. time slots). below.

Table 5. The upper table shows the total requested up-regulation in kWh. The lower table shows the proportion (in %) of this requested regulation, which was actually delivered regulation (i.e. the actual deviation from the baseline summed through the 15 min. time slots).

	2020-11-26	2020-12-03	2020-12-15	2020-12-17
FL16S			0	
FL17S			0	7.65
FL1S	0	0.86	0	3.46
FL27S	0	0.21		2.76
FL2S			0	0.31
FL7S		8.40		6.54

	2020-11-26	2020-12-03	2020-12-15	2020-12-17
FL16S			0	
FL17S			0	100
FL1S	0	90	0	73
FL27S	0	47		65
FL2S			0	0
FL7S		64		68

Again, we can see that there is a considerable amount of variation on both the requested regulation and the delivered proportion. It’s noted that in the 2020-11-26 and 2020-12-15 tests no down-regulation was requested – that was because the test were one-way tests in order to try to “push” the systems in only one direction. The analysis in the following will go into details and point out important aspects.

4.1.3.2. Detailed analysis

In this section we will try to point out the most valuable findings from the tests. The tests for three of the sites were not successful, the main reason for each is summarized:

- FL2S: has another heating source which was doing the heating.
- FL16S: both technical issues and other heating sources created problems.
- FL17S: some technical problems led to the heating system not really responding to control signals.

FL1S on 2020-12-03

The data from the test is shown below in Figure 27.

Figure 27. The upper three plots show: the baseline, requested modification, and the reference (baseline + modification) together with the observed power. In the lowest plot the indoor air temperature with comfort boundaries shown.

From this data we find the following:

- The baseline power was followed very close and the temperature was most of the time well inside the comfort bounds, which indicates that the model and optimisation behind the calculation of the baseline, works satisfactorily for FL1S.
- There seems to be a quite fast response in air temperature, when the HP is running, and a longer and slower response during the day – maybe caused by increasing outside air temperature, as well as solar radiation, during the day.
- The baseline has a quite peaky behaviour, opposed to a smooth operation at a lower power level - which probably is more appropriate for comfort.
- Only a short activation of regulation was carried out in the test. Actually, only a shift of consumption from a single 15 min. slot to the next was carried out. This results in too little data for concluding anything on how much flexibility potential is available in the system.

The other tests with FL1S have nearly the same results.

FL7S on 2020-12-17

Similar type of plots as above are presented for the test at FL7S on the 2020-12-17'th in Figure 28 below.

Figure 28. The upper three plots show: the baseline, requested modification, and the reference (baseline + modification) together with the observed power. In the lowest plot the indoor air temperature with comfort boundaries is shown.

From this data we conclude the following:

- In this test we can see that there are some challenges with the baseline model for FL7S. The calculated baseline is most of the times around twice the observed values, only a few times the observed is as high as the calculated. The HP is controlled with a temperature set point, so it seems that the model predicting the power as a function of the set point isn't well calibrated.
- The temperature is kept well inside the comfort bounds with the realized control sequence – hence following the calculated higher baseline, the temperature would most likely have exceeded the upper comfort bound.
- The building seems to have a quite slow decaying response, seen from the slow decrease at night time.

- The activation is not in very long periods, hence not really pushing the system to the limit, but rather shifting small peaks in the heating. With the slow response seen, this system has a high potential and could be “pushed” harder to the bounds with longer periods of regulation in one direction.

The result of the other test with FL7S is very similar.

FL27S on 2020-12-03

Same type of plots as for the tests presented above are presented in Figure 29 below.

Figure 29. The upper three plots show: the baseline, requested modification, and the reference (baseline + modification) together with the observed power. In the lowest plot the indoor air temperature with comfort boundaries are shown.

From this data we deduce the following:

- The baseline has in this case been calculated to a rather constant level, opposed to the baselines calculated for most of the other systems.
- From the observed power it’s seen that the heater was also run at a rather constant level, however it did shift in level during some periods, indicating that the control model isn’t fully accurate.

- So, the errors in the prediction are most likely due to starting at a too low temperature level, leading to higher power levels, when the temperature is too low. However, it’s a little strange why the requested decrease in power between 9:00 and 10:00 cannot be delivered, since at that point in time the temperature is above the lower comfort bound.

The other two tests with FL27S did have some issues due to a misunderstanding with the user and a technical problem, however the overall results were like the presented – most noticeable was the lack of response to the regulation.

4.1.4. Baseline forecasts

In this section an evaluation of the baseline forecasts is presented. It’s a short evaluation, simply due to the fact, that the data from successful tests were very limited and as such it’s not possible to generalize from these results.

We will first present the result from the successful test with FL1S on 2020-12-03, and then from the test with FL7S on 2020-12-17, both tests included in the detailed up- and –down-regulation analysis above.

FL1S on 2020-12-03

The plot in Figure 30 is of the forecast residuals and KPIs from the test.

Figure 30. In the upper plot: ‘Presidual’ is the observed forecast errors, i.e. residuals (‘Pobs’- ‘Pbase’). In the upper plot: ‘PresidualRMSE’ is the RMSE up to time t. In the lower plot: ‘PresidualAbsCumsum’ is the accumulated absolute error.

Note that the observations where activations occurred have been removed, since they of course should not be counted in the baseline forecast assessment. From the plots it can be seen that the observed forecast errors have a pattern different from white noise, however it’s not clear that the level increase with the horizon, which would be natural. The KPIs (or scores) are summarized in Table 6 below.

Table 6. The forecast KPIs (or scores). The normed scores are normed with the average observed power during the test.

	RMSE	MAE	Meanbias
Value (kW)	0.16	0.10	-0.03
Normed (%)	16.51	10.84	-3.14

A normalized RMSE of 16.6% for such forecasts, which have a horizon around 24 hours is a very good result – certainly also one of the best results from the tests.

FL7S on 2020-12-17

The plot in Figure 31 is of the forecast residuals and KPIs from the test.

Figure 31. Same type of plot as Figure 30 above.

The KPIs are shown in Table 7 below.

Table 7. The forecast KPIs (or scores). The normed scores are normed with the average observed power during the test.

	RMSE	MAE	Meanbias
Value (kW)	0.88	0.35	-0.19
Normed (%)	163.02	64.19	-34.26

In this case the forecast error is much higher than for the presented FL1S case. The level of the normalized RMSE is about 10 times higher. Clearly, in this case the model for forecasting can be improved.

4.2. Self-optimisation

As seen in Table 3 the self-optimisation (Spanish use case) tests were carried out 7 times for FL1S, and tried unsuccessfully once for FL2S. The description of the setting and the MPC optimisation model can be found in [1].

The best test for FL1S was on 2020-12-09, all others were stopped due to high temperatures, so we choose to present an analysis of the result from that day in the following. First it is noted

that there were a series of technical issues during the test. The thermostat of the HVAC system was not working properly, it didn't stop the device when the desired temperature was reached. So, an external sensor was used, however that created problems for the control. Further, the external sensor seemed biased, showing too high temperatures, compared to the set point.

In Figure 32 below the collected hourly values collected through the test are plotted. The following variables are included:

- Upper: ‘Pobs’ is the observed HP power.
- Second upper: ‘Psolar’ is the observed power from the PV at the site and ‘pvPower’ is calculated power to be consumed by the HP from the PV.
- Third upper: ‘gridPower’ is the calculated power to be consumed by the HP from the grid.
- Lower plot: ‘T’ is the indoor air temperature, ‘Tset’ is the actual realized HP temperature setpoint, ‘setpoint’ is the calculated optimal HP temperature setpoint, and the comfort boundaries are the two last.

Figure 32. Explanation of the variables plotted is in the text.

It can be seen that the optimisation started running at 07:00 UTC (the time points are set to the end of the hour). The optimisation calculates the three variables: ‘pvPower’, ‘gridPower’ and ‘setpoint’. *In the present plot, only the first calculated optimal solution is shown*, i.e. it’s the sequence calculated before 07:00 UTC, which is updated every hour from there (which is then seen as ‘Tset’). From this data it’s found that:

- The power (upper plot black line) is zero until 07:00 UTC, hence HP was not operating until then, which also explains the decreasing indoor temperature (lower plot black line).
- It can be seen that the HP runs high power when in the morning, leading to an increase in temperature such that it’s very close to the upper comfort bound (maybe it’s the sensor bias).
- The PV power forecast is low. It can be a simple cause of forecast errors, as seen in the solar power forecast evaluation in Section 2, this can be caused by errors in the NWP.
- The realized set point (Tset) is somewhat higher than the calculated, which is somewhat not as expected.

Similar findings are supported by the data from the other self-optimisation tests. So, there are issues with the MPC optimisation, which leads to unexpected behaviour, hence the MPC model and optimisation, must be further developed to be successfully deployed.

4.3. Conclusions from evaluation of tests results

The analysed data from the aFRR tests clearly indicates that the models behind the baseline calculation and subsequent control works as intended in several tests. The temperature is held within the comfort bounds and the control can follow the predicted baseline power well. However, it’s also clear that in many cases the baseline cannot be followed and temperatures can exceed the comfort bounds, which is not unexpected given that the predictions have a 10 to 34 hours horizon. This leads to the learning that this kind of control should focus on a shorter horizon and be frequently updated - which also is possible in the Dutch aFRR market, where so called “free bids” can be given all the way up to one hour before operation. In this way much more of the flexibility can be exploited, both because predictions become more accurate, but mostly because the available flexibility can be focused to the next few hours and doesn’t have to be “spread out” over 24 hours.

The tests were rather simple, where only short periods of activation were requested by the aggregator, which, as demonstrated in the short analysis of data from the aFRR, is not as in the real conditions, where activations can last many hours. In the most successful tests, all requests were successfully delivered, which proves that the setup is functional, however it didn’t “push” the systems allowing to conclude on the available flexibility in the systems – and in general not enough data was available to generalize on such matters.

Regarding the baseline forecasts it’s not possible to generalize about forecast performance, due to small amounts of available data. Clearly, aggregating many HPs will lead to a relatively

higher forecast accuracy - since from statistics we know, that if the forecast errors are independent, then the standard error of the mean (i.e. the “relative” sum) of the errors from all systems, decreases with $\frac{1}{\sqrt{n}}$. To increase the forecast accuracy running in a rolling setup with short horizons is found to be a good idea, since forecasting load 24 hours ahead accurately is challenging.

Finally, The MPC model, which was applied in the few self-optimisation tests seems to have flaws. Exactly what is the cause leading to the observed sub-optimal behaviour is hard to point out from the available data, but it’s clear that further development is required before the control and optimisation is functioning satisfactorily.

5. ECONOMIC COST-BENEFIT ANALYSIS

This section describes the economic aspect of the Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA) for the Horizon 2020 FLEXCoop project in order to investigate potential costs and benefits for involved economic entities, namely aggregators and prosumers. In this deliverable, the analysis is carried out considering the Dutch and the Spanish energy markets.

In order to investigate if the Demand Response (DR) integrated solution to be developed in the FLEXCoop project allows for a profitable business case for the involved stakeholders, resulting in an appropriate allocation of costs and benefits, a micro-level analysis is performed to estimate the impact of Distributed Energy Resources (DER) units integration in the power system as well as the performance of the Demand Response solution on involved economic parties [1].

5.1. CBA Objectives

Every single entity involved in a business scenario must be able to make a profit as no stakeholder is interested in a new product or service if its benefit is not evident.

As already depicted in [1], the concerned stakeholders in FLEXCoop are two, namely, aggregators (in the FLEXCoop context, cooperatives assume the role of an aggregator) and prosumers. The costs and/or benefits can be different for each one of them. Especially for prosumers the benefits can be of various types and not necessarily expressed in monetary terms (e.g. increase comfort, contribute in a “eco-friendlier” use of electricity, etc.). The economic CBA focuses on the monetary aspect and the potential economic incentives.

The economic aspect of the cost-benefit analysis (CBA) for the FLEXCoop project is aligned with the proposed CBA methodology presented in [1] taking into consideration the current project’s status.

Due to the differences between the case studies in the two countries [2], the decision to perform a micro-level CBA leads to the creation of distinct and separate analysis scenarios, each focused in a specific case study.

The context of the Dutch pilot site involves cooperatives which use their flexibility for providing balancing and ancillary services to other actors of the system (mainly the

Transmission System Operators (TSOs), but potentially also Distribution System Operators (DSOs), retailers or other cooperatives). The particular case is by participating in the aFRR market. We will denote the case study investigating benefits generated by participating in the aFRR market as “Case Study1 (CS1): Participation into Balancing and Ancillary Services (aFRR Market)”. CS1 is directly related to FLEXCoop Business Model BM3 in [2].

The context of the Spanish pilot site involves cooperatives which are power producers and retailers and propose the FLEXCoop solution to their customers in exchange for cheaper electricity (through increased self-optimisation or cheaper retail prices). Cooperatives can take the additional role of an aggregator in order to (a) valorise consumers’ flexibility to match prosumer’s assets generation period, or in order (b) to match low prices period on the wholesale market. We will denote the case study investigating benefits generated by increasing energy self-optimisation as “Case Study 2 (CS2): Self-optimisation”. CS2 is directly related to FLEXCoop Business Models BM1 and BM2 in [2].

To develop the economic CBA, as a first step, we analyse benefits and generate the potential different savings profiles that our analyses have identified for the two case studies. In the second step, based on the modelling established for estimating benefits, we analyse costs and generate the related different cost profiles for the two case studies. By combining savings profiles and applicable costs profiles, we create scenarios on which we extract results indicating the feasibility or not of each specific scenario.

5.2. Benefits Analysis

5.2.1. CS1: Introduction into the Dutch aFRR Market

The case of the Dutch pilot site is focused on the participation into balancing and ancillary services of the energy market. The balancing and ancillary services are procured from electricity generators, consumers and prosumers. These services can be used for different purposes and ensure access at all times to the needed resources to ensure reliable and stable electricity system operation.

The scenario taking place on the Dutch pilot site is the one where cooperatives use their flexibility for providing services to other actors of the system such as TSO, DSO, retailer or other cooperatives. Within the FLEXCoop context, in the Dutch pilot site, ODE, is acting as an independent aggregator in the role of Balancing Service Provider (BSP) and interacting with the TSO (TenneT) for participating in the automatic Frequency Restoration Reserve (aFRR) market.

In the Netherlands, in the coming 20 years there will be a heat transition. That means that heating of dwellings and buildings will not be done with gas anymore. As a result of this, there will be millions of heat pumps in the Netherlands installed in dwellings in the coming years. So, in the Dutch pilot site we combine two elements: (a) the possibility for the Dutch pilot cooperatives (Escozon and ODE Decentraal) to access to the Dutch aFRR market, and (b) the emerging trend related to the massive installation of heat pumps which use electricity and have potential flexibility.

A detailed description of the Dutch pilot site case, the Dutch aFRR market characteristics, regulations and mode of employment as well the operation of the involved FLEXCoop components is presented in [1], chapter 3.

5.2.2. CSI: Analysis of price and activation data from the Dutch aFRR balancing power market

An explanation and analysis of the prices and activations on the Dutch aFRR market is given in the following. The aim is to introduce the reader to how market is designed and how it is actually functioning - and eventually provide some figures of the revenue potential for delivering flexibility with heat pumps on this market. The aFRR balancing market is operated by the Dutch TSO [Tennet](#).

It will be necessary for a reader with no previous knowledge about the Dutch aFRR market to read about the design here the Implementation Regulations ([23]).

5.2.2.1. aFRR price and activation data

The data used is downloaded from [21].

5.2.2.1.1. Minutely values

First a small period is presented in order to introduce the market. The data between 1. Feb. and 7. Feb. 2020 is downloaded and only the needed variables are kept.

In all downloaded data the time points are at the beginning of the time intervals. This is changed such that the time point is set to the end of the interval.

First a plot of the minutely data for the week is generated of the variables:

- To.regulate.up: The activated up-regulation power in MW
- Highest_price_upward: The highest price of the activated bids
- To.regulate.down: The activated down-regulation power in MW
- Lowest_price_down: The lowest price of the activated bids (the revenue is the day-ahead price minus this)

Figure 33. Whole period: aFRR prices and activation

Plot of upward activation during a day (i.e. there is a lack of power, so the balancing power is increased to cover the need (i.e. demand is decreased):

Figure 34. Up regulation during a day

Same day, a plot of a downward activation (demand should be increased). Note the price flow: when it is negative, the TSO pays money (when its positive (as it is most of the time), the TSO receives money (a generator was already paid (more) on the day-ahead to produce, so still profitable if the price is below the day-ahead price):

Figure 35. Down-regulation during a day

It is noted that:

- Both activation levels and prices vary a lot within a 15 minutes interval
- The up and down activation events don't occur at the same minute intervals, however clearly within a 15 minutes interval it is possible that both ways are activated.

5.2.2.1.2. Quarterly values

The quarterly (15 min.) values of activation and prices are presented in this section, and it is explained how they are related with the minutely (1 min.) values. Quarterly values were downloaded from [22].

Data from the first days in Feb. 2020 are plotted, both the 1 min. and the 15. min. prices. In the Implementation Regulations it is stated that the settlement price (the price that is paid to all activated bids) is the highest activation price in the Imbalance Settlement Period (ISP), however as seen in the plot they are not always equal. We don't know the explanation for this, but maybe there are some corrections applied with the settlement price is calculated:

Figure 36. Quarterly and minutely prices: Up regulation.

For down-regulation the settlement price is the lowest price in the quarter:

Figure 37. Quarterly and minutely prices: Down regulation.

A scatter plot of the highest price in the 15 minutes interval vs. the settlement price of the interval. We don't dig further into this, and use the settlement prices from the 15 min. data in the remaining of this analysis:

Figure 38. Quarterly and highest minutely price scatter plot

5.2.2.2. Price vs. revenue

During a quarterly ISP the deliveries are, as presented above, activated in minutely slots. This is what is used for calculating the payment for delivery: settlement price multiplied with the activated energy. Hence in order calculate the potential revenue the minutely activation of regulating power must be analysed.

It is important to notice that calculating the fully realistic achievable revenue (both up and down) is in reality complicated. E.g. for up-regulation the energy is then not consumed as planned at the day-ahead, but must be consumed at another time to keep the total balance. In the following only the revenue of the delivered regulating energy is considered.

5.2.2.2.1. First week of February 2020

An analysis of the first week of February is presented in the following. In the week between 1. Feb. and 7. Feb. 2020 there were 672 quarterly ISPs.

5.2.2.2.2. Proportion of activation

Of these 339 had upward activation. Hence 50.4% of the ISPs. The actual activation occurs in minutely slots, which happened only 35.8% of the minutely slots in that week, hence the proportion which the smallest bid (1 MW) would be activated.

Considering a higher level of power, e.g. a 5 MW bid, on a minutely scale the maximum power, which could be have been activated in the period (relative to the full activation potential in all periods), is plotted as a function of the power level bid:

Figure 20. Proportion of up and down regulation activation for bid sizes

This leads to forming two variables, which will be used in the remaining analysis: The proportion of activation for up and down. For one direction:

- An amount of x MW was bid and accepted for a 15 min. ISP for the direction
- On a minutely scale it was always activated if there was activation in the given direction
- The value is then the proportion of the 1 MW which was activated during the 15 minutes

Hence, the assumption is that the bid had the lowest bid price (i.e. always activated) and there are no effects like ramping etc.

The following plots illustrate the variables of activated proportion up and down. Plotted both for a 1 MW bid and for a 10 MW bid. First the for the entire week, where it can be seen how there almost all the time is activation in either way:

Figure 39. Week of activated proportion up and down

A plot of only the two first days shows that given a 10 MW bid the proportion of activation is lower in many of ISPs (15 minutes slots), simply since the total activation was lower than 10 MW (at least in some of the minutely slots):

Figure 40. Two days of activated proportion up and down

5.2.2.2.3. Revenue

The revenue for a given direction can now be calculated for a bid of x MW for a given direction, simply by multiplying the activated proportion (for x MW) with the settlement price (divided by 4 going from EUR/MWh to EUR/MW given 15 min. ISPs).

5.2.2.2.4. Definition of revenue for up regulation

This will give the following revenue for a 1 MW bid up regulation (again with the assumptions stated, e.g. that the bid will always be activated (i.e. it has the lowest bid price)):

Figure 41. Revenue for up regulation

If the minutely level is neglected and it is only assumed that in each quarterly ISP 1 MW is always activated (in ISPs with activation), then the total revenue for this particular week would be 5377 EUR. (Note, as explained before, this is only the revenue which can be obtained delivering the regulating energy (less consumption)). However, again considering the actual activated power of a minutely level then the revenue for the week would be 4265 EUR, hence lower (note that it’s not the average weekly revenue, but for this particular week, which appears to be a week with high levels of activation and price).

Note that this proportion is higher compared to only considering the number of slots of activation (as the first example), since the periods with high price levels also are the periods with high activation.

5.2.2.2.5. Definition of revenue for down regulation

Calculating the revenue for down regulation in a similar way is trickier, since the settlement price for down regulation is what must be paid to consume more. It plotted for the week:

Figure 42. Down regulation price

So, when it is negative the prosumer will be directly paid to consume more, however often it is positive, thus it costs to consume more, however it is (often) more profitable to “buy” the energy at the regulation market vs. at the day-ahead market.

To separate the day-ahead and the regulation costs (or revenue), then we must consider both the day-ahead price and the down regulation price. Plotted for the week they are:

Figure 43. Down-regulation and day ahead price

It is seen that there are many periods with a higher down reg. price compared to the day-ahead price, however these are mostly when there is no downward activation. So, a first step is to multiply the difference with the activated down regulation (1 MW), as illustrated here forming “revenue_down_tmp” in the lower plot (zoom of two days):

Figure 44. Revenue for down regulation

It can be seen that there is still negative revenue in some ISPs, which seems less reasonable from an economic point of view.

To investigate this a little deeper box-plots for the distribution at the different proportion of activation (1 MW) is generated:

Figure 45. Price distribution for different levels of proportion of activation down

It is seen that for all levels of activation there are such negative revenue values. A similar plot for the entire 3 years period reveals similar patterns:

Figure 46. Price distribution for different levels of proportion of activation down (all 3 years) histogram of the non-zero values for the entire period:

Figure 47. Histogram of the non-zero values (all 3 year)

One could suspect that there was a timing error in the calculation in the activated proportion, however lagging it back or forward before calculating the revenue changes the distribution only marginally:

Figure 48. Histogram of the non-zero values for -1, 0 and 1 quarter lag (all 3 years)

Finally, it is decided to disregard the negative revenue values by setting them to zero. In total the proportion of revenue which is negative is around 10 %

5.2.2.3. Revenue for up regulation (decrease demand)

The price of up-regulation on aFRR in EUR/MWh in 15 min. ISPs, hence divide with 4 to get revenue per activated MW (revenue_up).

Plot for the entire period:

Figure 49. Revenue for up regulation (all 3 years)

Plot for a week in the winter:

Figure 50. Revenue for up regulation (winter week)

Plot for a week in the spring:

Figure 51. Revenue for up regulation (spring week)

5.2.2.4. Revenue for Down regulation (increase demand)

The price of down-regulation on aFRR in EUR/MWh in 15 min. ISPs, hence divide with 4 to get revenue per activated MW (revenue_up).

Plot for the entire period:

Figure 52. Revenue for down regulation (all 3 years)

Plot for a week in the winter:

Figure 53. Revenue for down regulation (winter week)

Plot for a week in the spring:

Figure 54. Revenue for down regulation (spring week)

5.2.2.5. Evenly strategy

In the following sections the different strategies applied for revenue calculations for a single simulated building with HP are presented. In this section it is the Evenly strategy and in the following section it is the Concentrate strategy.

5.2.2.5.1. Description

Evenly Distributed flexibility strategy. The flexibility is the difference between the electrical power at the baseline (21 °C) to the lower temperature (19 °C) (up reg.) and to the upper temperature (23 °C) (down reg.).

5.2.2.5.2. Simulations

The electrical power from simulations at the three different room temperature set points (19 °C, 21 °C and 23 °C).

A plot for the entire period is shown below. The upper plot is of the electrical power of the heat pump for the three temperature levels. The mid plot is the up-regulation which can be delivered under the Evenly bid strategy and similarly for the down-regulation is in the lower plot:

Figure 55. Delivered up and down regulation for the Evenly bid strategy (all 3 years)

It can be seen how the deliverable up-regulation power is rather stable in the winter, zero in the summer (the heating is off). There is an increased variation in the transition (spring and autumn).

Plot for a week in the winter:

Figure 56. Delivered up- and down-regulation for Evenly bid strategy (winter week)

It can be seen that the up-regulation power which can delivered is rather stable, except of one day (“2019-02- 03”) which is a sunny day, where the heating decreases.

Plot for a week in the spring:

Figure 57. Delivered up- and down-regulation for the Evenly bid strategy (spring week)

It can be seen that there is a high variation due to the solar radiation, and that the levels increase to high peaks in the evening due to the heating in the 23 °C scenario starts earlier in the evening than in the 21 °C scenario.

5.2.2.5.3. Up-regulation revenue

The revenue from delivering up-regulation under the Evenly bid strategy is calculated by multiplying the up-regulation power with the activated proportion (1 MW) with the revenue for up-regulation. The result is shown in the following plots.

For the entire period:

Figure 58. Up regulation revenue for the Evenly bid strategy (all 3 years)

It can be seen how, at least the peaks, the revenue (lower plot) is rather stable during the year (and of course zero in during the summer).

Plot for a week in the winter:

Figure 59. Up-regulation revenue for the Evenly bid strategy (winter week)

It can be seen how the revenue for activation varies quite a lot between the ISPs, which is because the price varies a lot. Hence in some ISPs there is a much higher revenue, not because more power is activated, but because the price is higher.

Plot for a week in the spring:

Figure 60. Up-regulation revenue for the Evenly bid strategy (spring week)

5.2.2.5.4. Down-regulation revenue

The revenue from delivering down-regulation under the Evenly bid strategy is calculated by multiplying the down-regulation power with the activated proportion (1 MW) with the revenue for down-regulation. The result is shown in the following plots.

Plot for the entire period:

Figure 61. Down regulation revenue for the Evenly bid strategy (all 3 years)

Compared to the up-regulation revenue it seems similarly stable, but less dominated by peaks (the peaks are fewer).

Plot for a week in the winter:

Figure 62. Down-regulation revenue for the Evenly bid strategy (winter week)

Seems to be at a higher level than the up-regulation and with a few high peaks.

Plot for a week in the spring:

Figure 63. Down-regulation revenue for the Evenly bid strategy (spring week)

As for up-regulation during sunny days no flexibility is available.

5.2.2.6. Concentrate strategy

In this section the Concentrate strategy for controlling a single simulated building with HP is presented.

5.2.2.6.1. Description

In the concentrate flexibility strategy, the heat pump is fully shut down (for up-reg.) or assumed to be able to be set to max power (for down-reg.).

The concentrate flexibility strategy is (done separately for up and down):

- For each day sort all ISPs according to the potential revenue
- Sum the flexibility (power or energy gives the same) for the Evenly strategy over the day
- Find the maximum number of the sorted ISPs, where the full power will not exceed the evenly distributed sum of power.
- Activate the full flexibility in those maximum revenue ISPs

In this way (assuming the prices and activation levels known) a reasonable compromise between using the full flexibility potential and temperature constrains is obtained.

By full power is meant:

- For up-reg. the electrical power in 21 °C simulation
- For down-reg. the difference between max. nominal power of the heat pump, set to 3 kW in the present case, and the electrical power in the 21 °C simulation

5.2.2.6.2. Up regulation revenue

Plot for the entire period:

Figure 64. Delivered up and down regulation for the Concentrate bid strategy (all 3 years)

Plot for a week in the winter:

Figure 65. Delivered up- and down-regulation for the Concentrate bid strategy (winter week)

Plot for a week in the spring:

Figure 66. Delivered up- and down-regulation for the Concentrate bid strategy (spring week)

5.2.2.6.3. Down-regulation revenue

Plot for the entire period:

Figure 67. Down regulation revenue for the Concentrate bid strategy (all 3 years)

Plot for a week in the winter:

Figure 68. Down-regulation revenue for the Concentrate bid strategy (winter week)

Plot for a week in the spring:

Figure 69. Down-regulation revenue for the Concentrate bid strategy (spring week)

5.2.2.7. Revenue and activation comparisons

In this section the revenue over the period of the two years is summarized for the strategies.

5.2.2.7.1. Revenue Per month

In Figure 70 below the monthly revenue for the two strategies is plotted. It’s calculated by summing up the revenues presented in the previous sections (series in lower plots of Figure 64 and Figure 67)

Figure 70. Monthly revenue for up- and down-regulation for both strategies

5.2.2.7.2. Average revenue per year

The results are the average revenue per year in EUR for the strategies, calculated by simply summarizing revenues presented in the previous sections. The revenue is per building, with the model presented in Section 3.1, i.e. a building heated with a heat pump and with the described parameter values, hence a representative case for single-family building living up to recent

building codes. As explained later this revenue has to be shared between the stakeholders, e.g. the aggregator and the building owner.

Up-regulation total revenue per year and representative building (EUR):

- EvenlyUp: 29 EUR
- ConentrateUp: 108 EUR

Down-regulation total revenue per year and representative building (EUR):

- EvenlyDown: 11 EUR
- ConcentrateDown: 39 EUR

Deliver only one way in each ISP (the most profitable way) per year and representative building (EUR):

- EvenlyEitherUpDown: 37 EUR
- ConcentrateEitherUpDown: 141 EUR

5.2.2.7.3. Delivered flexibility

The total energy delivered as up-regulation flexibility per year and representative building with the strategies are summarized (in kWh):

- Evenly strategy: 453 kWh
- Concentrate strategy: 811 kWh

The total energy delivered as down-regulation flexibility per year and representative building with the strategies are summarized:

- Evenly strategy: 475 kWh
- Concentrate strategy: 843 kWh

5.2.2.7.4. Average revenue when delivering flexibility

In periods where activated the average revenue when delivering up-reg. flexibility (in EUR/MW) for the strategies:

- Evenly strategy: 15 EUR/MW
- Concentrate strategy: 30 EUR/MW

In periods where activated the average revenue when delivering down reg. flexibility (in EUR/MW):

- Evenly strategy 6 EUR/MW
- Concentrate strategy: 12 EUR/MW

5.2.3. CS1: aFRR Market Discussion

The following is a discussion of the results and what must be taken into account regarding the assumptions and model simplifications for each of the two strategies.

It is clear that the concentrate strategy is able to generate a higher revenue, which can be explained by the fact that more flexibility is delivered (almost the double), and that it is delivered when the price is higher (again at double average price). Remember also, that the results presented are for a specific set of building parameters, different parameters would lead to different revenues etc. These relations should be examined in further studies.

The Evenly strategy misses out on opportunities to deliver, but on the other hand it is conservative and guarantees that the flexibility can be delivered at any time. This will allow it to be used for contracted bids. Contracted bids must be sent to the market at 14:45 the day before operation, and additional fixed payment for this is given (we do not know the exact amount and there are also other requirements to be taken into account).

The Concentrate strategy is unrealistic in that it would need a perfect price and activation forecast (which is impossible), but on the other hand it allows for more flexibility to be delivered, which is not unrealistic considering the very conservative Evenly strategy. This strategy will be suited for free bids, which are sent to the market 30 minutes in advance of operation. It might not be possible to forecast price and activation a day ahead (this should be investigated), but certainly on shorter horizons, so this information can be taken into account and strategies, where even more flexibility can be delivered seems possible.

Hence, the calculated revenue potentials for the Evenly should certainly be realizable, since it is very conservative, where the Concentrate might be unrealistic to achieve. However, it should be possible to deliver more flexibility than in the Evenly, maybe even more than in Concentrate, and by this achieve revenues closer to Concentrate in reality.

Finally, a few comments on the aFRR market constraints which will be hard to meet. First, it will be hard with many smaller systems to always reach the minimum bid size of one MW and make bids in quantities of one MW, certainly since the available flexibility varies with the climate. A few more assumptions are made e.g. minimum price bid assumed, hence the bids are always activated and ramping is assumed to be immediately (in reality the ramp rate is 7% per minute).

5.2.4. CS2: Introduction in Self-optimisation in Spain

The case of the Spanish pilot site is focused on cooperative retailer which proposes the FLEXCoop solution to its customers in exchange for cheaper electricity (through increased self-consumption or cheaper retail prices). Cooperatives which are power producers and retailers, assume the additional role of an aggregator in order to valorise consumers' flexibility to match prosumer's assets generation period, or in order to match low prices periods on the wholesale market.

Consumers' flexibility may in this case have different uses:

- a) related to self-consumption, by maximising energy consumption from local generation units (mainly PVs) at prosumer level when high Renewable Energy System (RES) generation exists.
- b) related to system efficiency, by optimising energy purchase from wholesale market based on price, surpluses rewards and deviations prices.

A detailed description of the Spanish pilot site case, the Spanish day ahead market characteristics, regulations and mode of employment, as well the operation of the involved FLEXCoop components, is presented in Chapter 4 of [1].

In the following section 5.2.5 a presentation is given of the model and optimisation used for calculating the potential revenue from applying MPC for self-optimisation in Spain - together with an analysis of one year data, covering entire 2019, where estimates of revenue for two representative buildings, at two different locations, are calculated.

5.2.5. CS2: Analysis of data from the Spanish market

The model is built using the structure presented in Figure 71. It is an extension of the MPC controlled state space model described in [29], which had only a heat pump and the thermal mass alone acted as heat storage for the system. The current model is extended to include a battery, PV modules and an electric heater, but the same principles are followed. A full mathematical description of the model, is given in the following sections.

Figure 71. *Model structure*

The model is a state space model derived from thermodynamic equations, where the heat dynamics of the building is represented by a lumped dynamic process model. The model parameters are defined based on the building composition and structure.

It is assumed, that the building is one big room with a flat roof. Thereto, the following assumptions have been made; a single uniform air temperature; no ventilation; no influence from humidity of the air; no influence from the wind. The dynamics of the electric heater and the heat pump are not modelled because their dynamics are much faster than those of the building - hence the only difference between using electrical heating vs. a heat pump is the COP, which sets the conversion factor from electricity to heat - and the heat pump can be used for both heating and cooling, which the electrical heater of course cannot.

5.2.5.1. State Space Equations

The state space model is defined by dividing the building into three zones; ‘Floor’, ‘Interior’ and ‘Envelope’. The envelope has an ‘Inner’ and an ‘outer’ part, referring to each side of the walls and roof, with the ‘Inner’ being on the inside of the insulation. The aim is to model the temperatures in each of the three zones. The thermodynamic relations of the model are equivalent to electric circuits, and can be illustrated with the RC-diagram shown in Figure 72.

Figure 72. The state-space model of the building illustrated as an RC-diagram.

The dynamics of the temperatures in the three zones are modelled by the linear continuous ordinary differential equations, called the system equations:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dT_t^f}{dt} &= \frac{1}{C_f} \left(\frac{T_t^i - T_t^f}{R_{f,i}} + (1 - \Psi_s)g_A\Phi_t^s + (1 - \Psi_h)\Phi_t^h \right) \\ \frac{dT_t^i}{dt} &= \frac{1}{C_i} \left(\frac{T_t^f - T_t^i}{R_{f,i}} + \frac{T_t^w - T_t^i}{R_{i,e}} + \Psi_s g_A\Phi_t^s + \Phi_t^h \Psi_h \right) \\ \frac{dT_t^w}{dt} &= \frac{1}{C_e} \left(\frac{T_t^i - T_t^w}{R_{i,e}} + \frac{T_a - T_t^w}{R_{e,a}} \right) \end{aligned}$$

Refer to the nomenclature list in Figure 73 below and Equation [29] for variable definitions and how they are calculated.

In order to use the model in the MPC it is discretized to a particular sampling period, e.g. hourly. The linear discrete time state space model is written as:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{x}_t &= \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x}_{t-1} + \mathbf{B}u_{t-1} + \mathbf{E}d_{t-1} \\ y &= \mathbf{C}\mathbf{x}_{t-1} + \epsilon_{t-1}, \end{aligned}$$

Where \mathbf{x} is the state vector (i.e. the three building zone temperatures) and u is the controllable input vector describing the heating power, which can be from a heat pump or an electric heater (as explained below it is a function of both the electrical power input and the COP factor). \mathbf{d} is the vector of disturbances, which in this case is the outdoor temperature and solar irradiation. Hence:

$$\mathbf{x}_t = \begin{bmatrix} T_t^i \\ T_t^f \\ T_t^w \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{u}_t = [\Phi_t^h] \quad \mathbf{d}_t = \begin{bmatrix} T_t^a \\ \Phi_t^s \end{bmatrix}$$

The heat input to the building is decided depending on the heat source: heat pump for heating, air conditioning or direct electrical heating, as well as where the electricity is charged from: the market, the PV or the battery. Hence:

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi_t^h = & COP_{hp}(u_t^{hp,market} + u_t^{hp,pv} + u_t^{hp,bat}) + \\ & COP_{ac}(u_t^{ac,market} + u_t^{ac,pv} + u_t^{ac,bat}) + \\ & u_t^{el,market} + u_t^{el,pv} + u_t^{el,bat} \end{aligned}$$

The matrix **A** specifies the dynamic behaviour of the system, whereas matrix **B** specifies how the controllable input signals enter the system, and **E** specifies the uncontrollable input signals. Furthermore, **C** is a constant matrix that specifies the controllable states, in the present case $\mathbf{C} = [1 \ 0 \ 0]$, such that y is the indoor temperature state called the controllable variable plus some error ϵ_{t} .

The MPC then becomes a linear programming problem formulated as:

$$\arg \min_{\mathbf{u}_s, v_k} \sum_{k=1}^N \lambda_{t+k} (u_{t+k}^{hp} + u_{t+k}^{ac} + u_{t+k}^{el} + u_{t+k}^{+,bat,market}) + p_k v_{t+k}$$

$$\text{subject to } \mathbf{X}_{s+1} = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{X}_s + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{u}_s + \mathbf{E}\mathbf{D}_s$$

$$T_{\min} \leq \mathbf{C}\mathbf{X}_{s+1} + v_{s+1}$$

$$T_{\max} \geq \mathbf{C}\mathbf{X}_{s+1} - v_{s+1}$$

$$0 \leq u_s^{hp,market} + (u_s^{hp,bat} + u_s^{hp,pv}) \cdot \eta_{inv} \leq P_{hp,max}$$

$$0 \leq u_s^{el,market} + (u_s^{el,bat} + u_s^{el,pv}) \cdot \eta_{inv} \leq P_{el,max}$$

$$-P_{ac,max} \leq u_s^{ac,market} + (u_s^{ac,bat} + u_s^{ac,pv}) \cdot \eta_{inv} \leq 0$$

$$0 \leq u_s^{+,bat,market} \cdot \eta_{inv} + u_s^{+,bat,pv} \cdot \eta_{conv} \leq \min(E_{bat,cap} - SoC_s \cdot E_{bat,cap}, P_{-,max})$$

$$0 \leq u_s^{hp,bat} \leq \min(SoC_s \cdot \eta_{inv} \cdot E_{bat,cap}, P_{-,max})$$

$$-\min(SoC_s \cdot \eta_{inv} \cdot E_{bat,cap}, P_{-,max}) \leq u_s^{ac,bat} \leq 0$$

$$0 \leq u_s^{el,bat} \leq \min(SoC_s \cdot \eta_{inv} \cdot E_{bat,cap}, P_{-,max})$$

$$0 \leq (u_s^{hp,pv} + (u_s^{ac,pv})/\eta_{inv} + u_s^{+,bat,pv}/\eta_{conv}) \leq P_s^{pv}$$

$$SoC_s \cdot E_{bat,cap} + u_s^{+,bat,market} \cdot \eta_{inv} + P_s^{+,pv} \cdot \eta_{conv} - (u_s^{hp,bat} - u_s^{ac,bat} + u_s^{el,bat})/\eta_{conv} = SoC_{s+1} \cdot E_{bat,cap}$$

$$\forall s \in \{t, t+1, t+2, \dots, t+N\}$$

Refer to the nomenclature in Figure 73 for variable descriptions.

We will dig deep into this description, just note the following main points:

- The upper equation is the economic objective function (starting with “arg min”), where it can be seen that the four electrical power variables, which are the electricity to be bought from the market. This function represents the costs of buying electricity which has to be minimized.
- The equations below the “subject to“ part sets the following constraints:
 - The building dynamics determines the development of the zone temperatures in the building.
 - There is an upper and a lower bound on the indoor air temperature.
 - The power for heating must be within 0 and a max capacity of the heating system.
 - The battery charging must be within limits of the battery capacity

The model is implemented in R with the `ctsm-r` package [25] which is then used for the discretization, and this is then passed as part of the MPC formulation to the `lpsolve` software for solving the linear programming problem (<https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/lpSolve/index.html> and <https://lpsolve.sourceforge.net>).

Nomenclature

Parameters

η_{conv}	Converter efficiency.	%
η_{inv}	Inverter efficiency.	%
COP_{hp}	AC COP factor.	-
COP_{hp}	HP COP factor.	-
$E_{bat,cap}$	Battery Capacity	kWh
P_{pv}	PV production	kW
$P_{ac,max}$	AC maximum power input.	kW
$P_{hp,max}$	HP maximum power input.	kW

Control variables

$u_{+,bat,market}$	Power bought on the market for charging the battery.	kW
$u_{+,bat,pv}$	Power produced by the PV for charging the battery.	kW
$u_{ac,bat}$	Cooling produced by AC using electricity from the battery	kW
$u_{ac,market}$	Cooling produced by AC using electricity from the market	kW
$u_{ac,pv}$	Cooling produced by AC using electricity from the PV	kW
$u_{el,bat}$	Heat produced by electric heater using electricity from the battery	kW
$u_{el,market}$	Heating produced by electric heater using electricity from the market	kW
$u_{el,pv}$	Heat produced by electric heater using electricity from the PV	kW
$u_{hp,bat}$	Heat produced by HP using electricity from the battery	kW
$u_{hp,market}$	Heating produced by HP using electricity from the market	kW
$u_{hp,pv}$	Heat produced by HP using electricity from the PV	kW

States

SoC	Battery State of Charge	%
T_t^f	Floor temperature	°C
T_t^i	Room temperature	°C
T_t^w	Wall temperature	°C

Inputs

Φ_t^s	Solar radiation	$\frac{kW}{m^2}$
T_t^a	Ambient temperature	°C

Figure 73. Nomenclature for the MPC model and linear programming formulation.

5.2.5.2. Analysis of scenarios

To quantify the potential savings from MPC optimisation of self-optimisation from PV panels, five different simulation scenarios was set up each for two different climate zones in Spain (Madrid and Barcelona).

The scenarios are:

1. Electric heater
2. Electric heater with PV panels
3. Electric heater with PV panels and a battery
4. Heat pump with PV panels
5. Heat pump with PV panels and a battery

Electric heaters are the most commonly used method for heating in Spain thus Scenario 1 is kept as the reference scenario.

The specifications of the system components are:

	Electric heater	Battery	Heat pump	DC/AC inverters	DC/DC converters	PV panels
Capacity	6 kW	8 kWh	1.5 kW			3 kWp
Efficiency	100%			80%	95%	

The system is controlled to optimize the operation costs by using the electricity price signals including VAT and taxes. The simulations were run for a whole year, using weather and price data from 2019. However, in Spain, a new three level regulation tax will in 2021 replace the current two-level regulation tax. Therefore, we have used the new regulation tax with the retail prices for 2019 to get more reliable result for the future, still keeping in mind that this might change and that there are actually different available regulation tax schemes in Spain. Finally, there is a compensation, which is an economic payment received by the PV owner for the energy fed into the grid, i.e. the energy not self-consumed.

The modelled building is a 132 m² single storey building. The properties, e.g. insulation and thermal mass, have been estimated using the 2013 building codes in Spain for Madrid (Appendix D and E in [31]). However, these are far from representative to the average houses in Spain, thus we use two insulation scenarios for this analysis;

- **High insulation** - estimated using the 2013 building codes in Spain for Madrid (Appendix D and E in [31]).
- **Low insulation** - adjusted the thermal insulation parameters ($R_{i,e}$ and $R_{e,a}$), to fit the average space heating demand in Madrid, which value is taken from the study in [32].

5.2.5.3. Simulation results

In the following tables, the results for all the scenarios are shown, for two different houses (Low insulation / High insulation) on two different locations (Barcelona/Madrid).

Table 8. Simulation results and related estimated annual savings for low insulation dwellings in Barcelona with and without MPC (figures in EUR/Year)

Barcelona - Low Insulation										
Profile	No MPC				MPC				Savings	
	Heat	Cool	Compen sation	Total	Heat	Cool	Compen sation	Total	%	EUR
Just electric heater	950 €			950 €	929 €			929 €	2,22%	21,11 €
Electric heater with PV	821 €		-133 €	688 €	793 €		-115 €	677 €	1,56%	10,70 €
Electric heater with PV and Battery	788 €		-119 €	668 €	707 €		-117 €	590 €	11,70%	78,20 €
Heat pump with PV	88 €	120 €	-120 €	88 €	85 €	103 €	-112 €	76 €	13,67%	12,01 €
Heat pump with PV and Battery	60 €	79 €	-102 €	38 €	47 €	61 €	-97 €	11 €	72,03%	27,14 €

Table 9. Simulation results and related estimated annual savings for high insulation dwellings in Barcelona with and without MPC (figures in EUR/Year)

Barcelona - High Insulation										
Profile	No MPC				MPC				Savings	
	Heat	Cool	Compen sation	Total	Heat	Cool	Compen sation	Total	%	EUR
Just electric heater	333 €			333 €	287 €			287 €	13,85%	46,17 €
Electric heater with PV	261 €		-155 €	106 €	224 €		-149 €	75 €	29,30%	31,07 €
Electric heater with PV and Battery	250 €		-151 €	99 €	189 €		-150 €	39 €	60,89%	60,36 €
Heat pump with PV	19 €	83 €	-136 €	-34 €	16 €	75 €	-132 €	-41 €	19,63%	6,76 €
Heat pump with PV and Battery	3 €	43 €	-121 €	-75 €	2 €	34 €	-118 €	-82 €	10,24%	7,66 €

Table 10. Simulation results and related estimated annual savings for low insulation dwellings in Madrid with and without MPC (figures in EUR/Year)

Madrid – Low Insulation										
Profile	No MPC				MPC				Savings	
	Heat	Cool	Compen sation	Total	Heat	Cool	Compen sation	Total	%	EUR
Just electric heater	1.388 €			1.388 €	1.360 €			1.360 €	2,02%	28,06 €
Electric heater with PV	1.225 €		-138 €	1.087 €	1.198 €		-129 €	1.069 €	1,69%	18,38 €
Electric heater with PV and Battery	1.198 €		-127 €	1.070 €	1.093 €		-127 €	966 €	9,75%	104,31€
Heat pump with PV	148 €	128 €	-125 €	151 €	145 €	117 €	-120 €	142 €	6,05%	9,15 €
Heat pump with PV and Battery	119 €	77 €	-103 €	94 €	94 €	62 €	-99 €	56 €	39,96%	37,48 €

Table 11. Simulation results and related estimated annual savings for high insulation dwellings in Madrid with and without MPC (figures in EUR/Year)

Madrid - High Insulation										
Profile	No MPC				MPC				Savings	
	Heat	Cool	Compen sation	Total	Heat	Cool	Compen sation	Total	%	EUR
Just electric heater	526 €			526 €	462 €			462 €	12,17%	64,00 €
Electric heater with PV	430 €		-162 €	268 €	372 €		-154 €	218 €	18,81%	50,41 €
Electric heater with PV and Battery	413 €		-156 €	257 €	320 €		-156 €	164 €	36,12%	92,88 €
Heat pump with PV	39 €	92 €	-143 €	-12 €	36 €	87 €	-141 €	-18 €	47,25%	5,89 €
Heat pump with PV and Battery	21 €	63 €	-124 €	-40 €	16 €	34 €	-122 €	-72 €	78,27%	31,47 €

When running the simulations without the MPC (No MPC), we basically just control the heater as a thermostatic proportional control, so it will be heating to keep the minimum temperature. We can draw some overall conclusions from this:

- There is not much flexibility available in a poorly insulated house (from Table 8. Simulation results and related estimated annual savings for low insulation dwellings in Barcelona with and without MPC (figures in EUR/Year) and Table 10, first Scenario “Just electric heater”, savings of around 2% with MPC is achieved). If the house insulation is high, we increase the flexibility significantly (from Table 9 and Table 11,

same scenario, we now get savings around 12%-14% with MPC). However, we begin to see some flexibility when adding the battery.

- Generally, the scenarios using the HP adds more flexibility than the electric heater because;
 - we get 3-4 times more heat out of each bought kWh, hence we can store more cheap energy from the grid when available.
 - we get 3-4 times more heat out of every PV produced kWh.
 - we can, store, so to speak, 3-4 times more “heat” using the battery. (Of course, it will not become heat until we discharge the battery by running the heat pump).
- However, considering the absolute savings, rather than the relative savings (percentages), it is clear that they there are generally not that big as the difference in the savings between electric heater and heat pump, simply because the overall operation costs drop significantly for the heat pump.
- With a well-insulated house, we would even earn money because the compensation for all the excess PV power is higher than what we pay for electricity on the market. Note that actually it’s not possible to get compensated like that, however in a setting with other electrical consumption adding to the total consumption, such negative total costs will be avoided.
- Note, for Madrid;
 - A well-insulated house spends more electricity on cooling than on heating.
 - A badly insulated house spends more electricity on heating than on cooling.
 - This may sound strange, but can be explained by the incoming heat from direct solar radiation through the windows, which is not depended on the insulation. Therefore, with high insulation it stays within the house for longer and requires more cooling.

In order to get more insights into how the model and optimisation behaves, results from some selected days are presented and analysed for “Madrid – fitted to average consumption” for Scenario 1, 3 and 5, in the following.

5.2.5.4. Scenario 1: Just electric heater

In Figure 74 below a plot of the relevant signals from four days is plotted for the setting where no MPC is applied. We can see how the thermostatic control (no MPC) runs the heaters with exactly the needed heat to maintain the minimum temperature. As seen in Figure 75 below, where same signals are plotted for the same period, for the setting where MPC calculate the heat input, we can see how we start to utilize the cheap electricity during the night to decrease the amount electricity needed when the prices are high. The total savings here are limited though, because very little heat is stored in the building mass. As one can see, the temperature decays to the lower bound fast (within an hour) which tells us the flexibility potential is low.

Figure 74. Scenario with electric heater;

Simple control (no use of MPC). Electric heater with PV and Battery: The upper plot is of the electricity price and electrical power signals in the objective function. The lower plot is of the indoor temperature and boundaries. The lower temperature boundary shifts between a nightly and a daily level – the daily period starts 8 in the morning and ends at 23 in the evening.

Figure 75. Just electric heater: MPC. Same as plot in Figure 74 above.

5.2.5.5. Scenario 3: Electric heater with PV and Battery

In this scenario a battery and PV modules are added to the system, and we begin to see some good use of the flexibility. Taking a look at Figure 76 it can be seen that the battery is never in use when the simple control is used. The reason is that the PV production is never large enough to exceed the demand from the electric heater. If we start to use the MPC, see Figure 77, we get a quite different result. First of all, we use mainly the battery for charging with electricity from the market during the night when the power is cheap. Then, occasionally, it is beneficial to store a small portion of the PV power for use later. That is because the PV power peaks when the market price is low, hence here we can use the cheap power from the market and save the PV power for later when the price goes high.

Figure 76. Electric heater with PV and Battery.

Simple control (no use of MPC): The Upper plot is of the electricity price and electrical power signals in the objective function. Middle plot is of the indoor temperature and boundaries, and the lower plot is the SoC and charge from market and PV.

Figure 77. Electric heater with PV and battery. Control with MPC. Same type of plots as in Figure 76 above.

5.2.5.6. Scenario 5: Heat pump with PV and Battery

Now, a heat pump is used instead of electrical heaters. In Figure 78 below, it is seen that with the simple control, the battery actually starts to store some electricity. This is because the heat pump is so efficient, that it cannot use all the PV power at once, as it with the electric heater. The stored energy is immediately used when the sun sets.

Figure 78. Heat pump with PV and battery; Simple control (no use of MCP)

If we apply the MPC, see Figure 79

Figure 79. Heat pump with PV and battery; MPC, we see a use similar to what we saw in with electrical heaters with PV and battery. However, we get to store more PV power, since we need less for running the heat pump. Another point noticed is the power bought on the market for storage. We don't use all the battery capacity every night, some nights we only charge a small amount. The reason is that we only buy what we need for the next 24 hours. Notice, Jan 31st, we actually don't buy electricity from the market during the day, we only use the stored electricity, which is sufficient.

Figure 79. Heat pump with PV and battery; MPC

As another benefit of the heat pump, we also produce cooling in the summer. This is likely where we utilize this concept the most due to the increased PV production in the summer.

Below, in Figure 80, we see a simulation of 3 days during the summer. First of all, the PV production always exceeds the demand, thus the excess power is stored every day to be used when the sun sets.

Figure 80. Heat pump with PV and battery; Simple control (no use of MPC); Summer

If we apply the MPC again, see Figure 81, we now see the battery charge reaching the full capacity of 8 kWh. Since the PV production is more than enough to charge the battery to the fullest, the MPC will no longer buy electricity from the market to store in the battery as it did in the winter.

Figure 81. Heat pump with PV and battery; MPC; Summer

5.2.5.7. Building mass for heat storage

In all previous simulations the indoor temperature drops quite fast, as previous explained this is due to the combination of the heat entering directly into the indoor air and the insulation level being low. As a result, the use of building mass for heat storage is rather infeasible. To illustrate, that building mass, in fact, can be used as storage and increase flexibility, Scenario 1 (with electrical heating) for the house “Madrid - High Insulation” - see Figure 82, was carried out. Notice, the decay during the nights when the heat is turned off – it is clear that the temperature does not decrease to the set point within an hour as in the low insulation case, but rather two or three hours. This means the house can keep warm for longer and thus increase flexibility, which is utilized every night in this case.

Figure 82. Electrical heating with insulation levels according to the most recent building codes. The same type of plots of power and temperature as previous.

5.2.5.8. Conclusions

The analysis of data from the Spanish market has produce the following conclusions:

- Generally, the scenarios using the HP adds more flexibility than the scenarios with the electric heater, since for the HP scenarios: there will be 3 to 4 times more heat from the bought electricity, there will be 3 to 4 times more heat out PV generated electricity, and similarly it's possible to store 3 to 4 times more “heat” using the battery. However, the absolute savings are larger when using the electric heater, because there are much higher operation costs.
- Results indicate that with low insulation levels the potential for storing heat in the building structure is very limited. In the model the heat from the heat pump or the electrical heaters flows directly into the indoor air, hence the air, which has a relatively low heat capacity, is very quickly heated up, however it takes long time before the heavier building parts (floor and interior) is similarly heated up – thus these parts hardly get activated as heat storage.
- A battery allows for direct storage of electricity; hence it can easily be used for shifting consumption in time. This is clearly seen in the simulations, where the “No MPC” simply charges when there is surplus power from the PV and discharges if it would otherwise buy from the market – without considering the price. The MPC can really exploit the battery by charging it when there is surplus PV, but also when the price is low.
- The economic potential of MPC optimisation depends highly on the building and the heating system components available. If no battery is available, then it is absolutely crucial to have a good level of insulation, otherwise the MPC will not make a difference when the heat enters directly into the indoor air – opposed to for example floor heating, where the heat enters directly into thermally heavy building parts as discussed in [29].
- Comparing the savings achieved in the scenarios in the two climate zones, it is found that in the colder zone (Madrid), as more heating is needed, the absolute savings are increased – mostly for the scenarios with battery, but only slight for scenarios without. This could be offset by an increase in the need for cooling however in the present two zones this was not the case.

- The impact of model deficiencies, such as the fact that the model is simple, i.e. effects such wind impact, occupants, are not included. In a real setting the model used for control will match the present used, however the real building will of course be much more complicated. Furthermore, the parameters have been set as reasonable as possible according to building codes, however it is of course always unknown how parameter uncertainties affect the results.
- From the estimated potential of savings in the different scenarios, it is clear that there is not much to gain with MPC in the low insulated cases, without a battery. Although it must be taken into account that the results are based on the particular prices of 2019 (with 2021 tariff scheme) – hence in the future the price might be more volatile the economic potential can increase – we find that it is very important to take into account the properties of the buildings, where MPC is rolled out. Such that well insulated buildings are preferred, or some energy storage solution is available. Batteries are very expensive today, so other heat storage solutions should be explored (water tanks, although not so efficient with heat pumps, or phase change materials).
- There is a need to further studies, where similar types of simulations are carried out. It would be highly relevant to use advanced building simulation software, such that the impact of model deficiencies is minimized. This should be carried out in combination with experiments in real representative building in order to verify the simulation results.

5.2.6. Savings Profiles

Collecting the data presented in sections:

- 5.2.2.7.2 for the Dutch market
- 5.2.5.3 for the Spanish market

And identifying the estimated potential annual revenue or savings per analysed case, we create the saving profiles presented in Table 12.

Table 12. Saving Profiles according to Service Type, Location and Dwelling Type

Id	Location	Dwelling Type	Service Type	Description	Annual Savings
SP-N1	The Netherlands	-	Balancing Services	Minimum Annual Revenue Per Dwelling/Heat Pump in Balancing Services for Dutch dwelling	37 €
SP-N2	The Netherlands	-	Balancing Services	Maximum Annual Revenue Per Dwelling/Heat Pump in Balancing Services for Dutch dwelling	141 €
SP-BL1	Spain - Barcelona	Low Insulation	Self-optimisation	Annual Savings of Barcelona low-insulation dwelling with just electric heater	21,11 €

Id	Location	Dwelling Type	Service Type	Description	Annual Savings
SP-BL2	Spain - Barcelona	Low Insulation	Self-optimisation	Annual Savings of Barcelona low-insulation dwelling with electric heater with PV	10,70 €
SP-BL3	Spain - Barcelona	Low Insulation	Self-optimisation	Annual Savings of Barcelona low-insulation dwelling with electric heater with PV and Battery	78,20 €
SP-BL4	Spain - Barcelona	Low Insulation	Self-optimisation	Annual Savings of Barcelona low-insulation dwelling with heat pump with PV	12,01 €
SP-BL5	Spain - Barcelona	Low Insulation	Self-optimisation	Annual Savings of Barcelona low-insulation dwelling with Heat pump with PV and Battery	27,14 €
SP-BH1	Spain - Barcelona	High Insulation	Self-optimisation	Annual Savings of Barcelona high-insulation dwelling with just electric heater	46,17 €
SP-BH2	Spain - Barcelona	High Insulation	Self-optimisation	Annual Savings of Barcelona high-insulation dwelling with electric heater with PV	31,07 €
SP-BH3	Spain - Barcelona	High Insulation	Self-optimisation	Annual Savings of Barcelona high-insulation dwelling with electric heater with PV and Battery	60,36 €
SP-BH4	Spain - Barcelona	High Insulation	Self-optimisation	Annual Savings of Barcelona high-insulation dwelling with heat pump with PV	6,76 €
SP-BH5	Spain - Barcelona	High Insulation	Self-optimisation	Annual Savings of Barcelona high-insulation dwelling with Heat pump with PV and Battery	7,66 €
SP-ML1	Spain - Madrid	Low Insulation	Self-optimisation	Annual Savings of Madrid low-insulation dwelling with just electric heater	28,06 €
SP-ML2	Spain - Madrid	Low Insulation	Self-optimisation	Annual Savings of Madrid low-insulation dwelling with electric heater with PV	18,38 €

Id	Location	Dwelling Type	Service Type	Description	Annual Savings
SP-ML3	Spain - Madrid	Low Insulation	Self-optimisation Maximisation	Annual Savings of Madrid low-insulation dwelling with electric heater with PV and Battery	104,31 €
SP-ML4	Spain - Madrid	Low Insulation	Self-optimisation	Annual Savings of Madrid low-insulation dwelling with heat pump with PV	9,15 €
SP-ML5	Spain - Madrid	Low Insulation	Self-optimisation Maximisation	Annual Savings of Madrid low-insulation dwelling with Heat pump with PV and Battery	37,48 €
SP-MH1	Spain - Madrid	High Insulation	Self-optimisation	Annual Savings of Madrid high-insulation dwelling with just electric heater	64,00 €
SP-MH2	Spain - Madrid	High Insulation	Self-optimisation Maximisation	Annual Savings of Madrid high-insulation dwelling with electric heater with PV	50,41 €
SP-MH3	Spain - Madrid	High Insulation	Self-optimisation	Annual Savings of Madrid high-insulation dwelling with electric heater with PV and Battery	92,88 €
SP-MH4	Spain - Madrid	High Insulation	Self-optimisation Maximisation	Annual Savings of Madrid high-insulation dwelling with heat pump with PV	5,89 €
SP-MH5	Spain - Madrid	High Insulation	Self-optimisation	Annual Savings of Madrid high-insulation dwelling with Heat pump with PV and Battery	31,47 €

5.3. Costs Analysis

In this section we perform the analysis of costs and present all the related factors that are applicable to both pilot sites, that is, to both case studies and the respective savings profiles identified in section 5.2.6.

5.3.1. DR measure cost (OSB Cost)

This is the actual cost of the, FLEXCoop essential, OSB module which enables smart home interoperability and ensures deployment of human-centric demand response strategies. The

hardware implementation of the OSB has been specified in [8] and [9]. A detailed list accompanied with the related cost of the hardware components required for an OSB to be constructed is provided in the table below:

Table 13. OSB Hardware Cost

NN	COMPONENT	DESCRIPTION	UNIT PRICE	QUANTITY	TOTAL PRICE
1	RPI 3B+	Main Processor Unit	32.97 €	1	32.97 €
2	DC Power	Power Supply	7.95 €	1	7.95 €
3	32GB MicroSD	Internal Memory	11.94 €	1	11.94 €
4	RPI Case	Gateway Casing	10.32 €	1	10.32 €
5	TSL25651	Luminance Sensor	5.89 €	1	5.89 €
6	CCS811	Air Quality Sensor	20.08 €	1	20.08 €
7	DHT22	Temperature Humidity Sensor	5.56 €	1	5.56 €
8	PaPIR	Motion Sensor	7.98 €	3	23.94 €
9	RPI Hat	Custom PCB	4.00 €	1	4.00 €
10	Zwave Antenna	Zwave Controller	41.33 €	1	41.33 €
Grand Total					163.98 €

The OSB module cost is 163.98 €. This capital expense is required once per end-user's dwelling.

At present, it should be noted, that in this cost of the OSB as a prototype device and not a commercial one. The commercial version should include industrial assembly and packing as well as further business-related costs that should be considered for the commercialisation of the device (e.g. marketing, testing, maintenance, etc.).

Furthermore, OSB includes also a software implementation as it is also described in detail in [8] and [9]. The estimation of this software development relevant costs should also be considered when referring in deployments of the FLEXCoop solution in contexts outside the project's pilot sites.

5.3.2. Dwelling Costs

Besides the OSB, the FLEXCoop Solution requires the provision or purchase of additional devices like power metering devices, sensors and actuators, gateways etc. This equipment needs to be installed in the prosumers' dwellings in order to, mainly, monitor, acquire data and control the Heat Ventilation and Cooling (HVAC) devices in a fully automated manner. Once installed

and customised these are the only devices alongside the OSB required for the operation of the FLEXCoop Solution. The acquisition of all the required monitor and control devices is part of the initial capital costs per dwelling. These costs are completed with the cost of the installation service required to install and setup the devices (including the OSB) and their inter-communication.

However, there are types of HVAC devices that cannot be control by commercially available devices installed on premises. In our pilot sites there are specific types of heat pumps that are vendor-locked and can be monitored and control through the vendor’s cloud platform. For example, NIBE heat pumps need the NIBE Uplink platform ([27]) to access automatic monitor and control functionality.

The NIBE Uplink platform offers 3 services:

- Basic service (quick overview and current status of device, access to one month of history data, email messaging for notifications)
- Premium service - Change settings (remote control of heat pump)
- Premium service – History (extended and complete historic information with diagrams)

The premium services, each has a subscription cost of 25€ per year. In the current status of the project, both services are required and employed in our pilot sites. For the market-ready FLEXCoop solution we can assume all data will be stored in the platform’s infrastructure and so, only the service for controlling the heat pump will be required. This cost is the annual operational cost per dwelling.

Taking into account the modelling for the estimation of benefits in section 5.2, we distinguish the following indicative Bills of Material (BoMs) from our Dutch and Spanish pilot sites in Table 14, Table 15, Table 16, Table 17 and Table 18 respectively:

- BoM1 – Indicative BoM for Dutch dwellings with heat pump controlled through monitor and control device.
- BoM2 - Indicative BoM for Dutch dwellings with heat pump controlled through vendor's cloud platform.
- BoM3 - Indicative BoM for Spanish dwellings with electric heaters (without heat pump).
- BoM4 - Indicative BoM for Spanish dwellings with heat pump controlled through monitor and control device.
- BoM5 - Indicative BoM for Dutch dwellings with heat pump controlled through vendor's cloud platform.

Table 14. BoM1 – Indicative BoM for Dutch dwellings with heat pump controlled through monitor and control device

INDICATIVE DEVICE NAME	INDICATIVE UNIT PRICE	QUANTITY	TOTAL PRICE
<i>Power Metering</i>			
Z-Wave Plus Aeotec Home Energy Meter - three clamps (60A)	100€	2	200€

<i>HVAC System Control + Sensing</i>			
IntesisBox IS-IR-WMP-1	142€	1	142€
Z-Wave Plus Aeotec MultiSensor 6	60€	2	120€
<i>Generic Devices</i>			
Z-Wave Plus Aeotec Range Extender 7 – EU	43€	1	43€
<i>DR Measurement</i>			
OSB	164€	1	164€
<i>BoM Indicative Grand Total</i>			669€

Table 15. BoM2 - Indicative BoM for Dutch dwellings with heat pump controlled through vendor's cloud platform

INDICATIVE DEVICE NAME	INDICATIVE UNIT PRICE	QUANTITY	TOTAL PRICE
<i>Power Metering</i>			
Z-Wave Plus Aeotec Home Energy Meter - three clamps (60A)	100€	2	200€
<i>HVAC System Control + Sensing</i>			
Z-Wave Plus Aeotec MultiSensor 6	60€	2	120€
<i>Generic Devices</i>			
Z-Wave Plus Aeotec Range Extender 7 – EU	43€	1	43€
<i>DR Measurement</i>			
OSB	164€	1	164€
<i>BoM Indicative Grand Total</i>			527€

Table 16. BoM3 - Indicative BoM for Spanish dwellings with electric heaters (without heat pump)

INDICATIVE DEVICE NAME	INDICATIVE UNIT PRICE	QUANTITY	TOTAL PRICE
<i>Power Metering</i>			
Z-Wave Plus Aeotec Home Energy Meter - three clamps (60A)	100€	1	100€
<i>HVAC System Control + Sensing</i>			
Z-Wave Plus Aeotec Aeotec Smart Switch 6 - EU	58€	3	174€
Z-Wave Plus Aeotec MultiSensor 6	60€	3	180€

Generic Devices			
Z-Wave Plus Aeotec Range Extender 7 – EU	43€	1	43€
DR Measurement			
OSB	164€	1	164€
BoM Indicative Grand Total			661€

Table 17. BoM4 - Indicative BoM for Spanish dwellings with heat pump controlled through monitor and control device

INDICATIVE DEVICE NAME	INDICATIVE UNIT PRICE	QUANTITY	TOTAL PRICE
Power Metering			
Z-Wave Plus Aeotec Home Energy Meter - three clamps (60A)	100€	1	100€
HVAC System Control + Sensing			
IntesisBox IS-IR-WMP-1	142€	1	142€
Z-Wave Plus Aeotec MultiSensor 6	60€	2	120€
Generic Devices			
Z-Wave Plus Aeotec Range Extender 7 – EU	43€	1	43€
DR Measurement			
OSB	164€	1	164€
BoM Indicative Grand Total			569€

Table 18. BoM5 - Indicative BoM for Dutch dwellings with heat pump controlled through vendor's cloud platform

INDICATIVE DEVICE NAME	INDICATIVE UNIT PRICE	QUANTITY	TOTAL PRICE
Power Metering			
Z-Wave Plus Aeotec Home Energy Meter - three clamps (60A)	100€	1	100€
HVAC System Control + Sensing			
IntesisBox IS-IR-WMP-1	142€	1	142€
Z-Wave Plus Aeotec MultiSensor 6	60€	2	120€
Generic Devices			
Z-Wave Plus Aeotec Range Extender 7 – EU	43€	1	43€

DR Measurement			
OSB	164€	1	164€
BoM Indicative Grand Total			569€

Taking into consideration the possible cost of the service to monitor and control the heat pumps as well as an installation fee of 120 € that presents a maximum 2-hour installation service per dwelling by an experienced local contractor to install and setup the related ICT equipment for the market-ready FLEXCoop solution we define the potential cost profiles for dwellings presented in Table 19.

Table 19. Cost profiles of dwellings including costs of BoM, equipment installation and potential service subscriptions

Id	Description	Applicable BoM	BoM Cost	BoM Installation Costs	Annual Subscription Cost	Total Dwelling Initial Costs	Total Dwelling Annual Costs
CP-DD	Cost Profile of Dutch dwelling with heat pump controlled through monitor and control device	BoM1	669€	120€	0€	789€	0€
CP-DC	Cost Profile of Dutch dwellings with heat pump controlled through vendor's cloud platform	BoM2	527€	120€	25€	647€	25€
CP-SN	Cost Profile of Spanish dwelling with electric heaters (without heat pump)	BoM3	661€	120€	0€	781€	0€
CP-SD	Cost Profile of Spanish dwellings with heat pump controlled through monitor	BoM4	569€	120€	0€	689€	0€

Id	Description	Applicable BoM	BoM Cost	BoM Installation Costs	Annual Subscription Cost	Total Dwelling Initial Costs	Total Dwelling Annual Costs
	and control device						
CP-SC	Cost Profile of Spanish dwellings with heat pump controlled through vendor's cloud platform	BoM5	427€	120€	25€	547€	25€

It should be noted that installation costs during the project's deployment phase have been registered considerably higher than the ones depicted in Table 19 due to multiple visits, equipment connection problems, etc.

5.3.3. FLEXCoop Solution Costs

The current state of the solution needs further development after the project ends to be considered market ready. The highest TRL achieved at the end of the project would be TRL 7 (mainly TRL 6 for most components).

In [4] we have developed a financial plan for the FLEXCoop Solution to provide financial indications for a potential joint venture between FLEXCoop partners. In this plan the FLEXCoop solution is offered as a platform/service (SaaS) to the aggregators.

Table 20 presents the aggregator's capital expenses to adopt the integrated FLEXCoop Solution.

Table 20. FLEXCoop Solution Initial Capital Costs

FLEXCOOP SOLUTION CAPITAL COST DESCRIPTION	AMOUNT
Platform Setup and Customisation	3.000 €
Training Fees (5 days – 6 hours per training per day)	2.000 €

Table 21 presents the FLEXCoop Solution's annual operational costs. Regarding the solution's annual operational costs, the financial plan distinguishes two cases, sales made directly by the FLEXCoop Joint Venture and sales made through a cooperatives network (at a national or European level). In the latter case, there is a 10% discount rate for the license fees.

Table 21. FLEXCoop Solution Annual Operational Costs

FLEXCOOP SOLUTION OPERATIONAL COST DESCRIPTION	AMOUNT
Platform Annual License Fee (direct sale)	12.000 €
Platform Annual License Fee (sale through cooperatives network)	10.800 €
Additional Annual License Fee per Prosumer/Member (direct sale)	40 €
Additional Annual License Fee per Prosumer/Member (sale through cooperatives network)	36 €

These initial capital and operational costs are the same for both the Dutch and Spanish pilot sites, that is for the case studies presented in [1] and this report, since both pilots use the whole FLEXCoop solution.

5.4. Results

By combining all the savings profiles of Table 12 with the applicable cost profiles of Table 19 we create the set of different scenarios we can examine for our two case studies. The available scenarios are presented in Table 22.

Table 22. Set of available different scenarios in the two case studies

Id	Savings Profile	Cost Profile	Description
CS1-N1-DD	SP-N1	CP-DD	Minimum Annual Revenue Per Dwelling/Heat Pump in Balancing Services for Dutch dwelling with heat pump controlled through monitor and control device
CS1-N1-DC	SP-N1	CP-DC	Minimum Annual Revenue Per Dwelling/Heat Pump in Balancing Services for Dutch dwelling with heat pump controlled through vendor's cloud platform
CS1-N2-DD	SP-N2	CP-DD	Maximum Annual Revenue Per Dwelling/Heat Pump in Balancing Services for Dutch dwelling with heat pump controlled through monitor and control device
CS1-N2-DC	SP-N2	CP-DC	Maximum Annual Revenue Per Dwelling/Heat Pump in Balancing Services for Dutch dwelling with heat pump controlled through vendor's cloud platform

Id	Savings Profile	Cost Profile	Description
CS2-BL1-SN	SP-BL1	CP-SN	Minimum Annual Revenue Per Dwelling/Heat Pump in Balancing Services for Dutch dwelling with heat pump controlled through monitor and control device
CS2-BL2-SN	SP-BL2	CP-SN	Minimum Annual Revenue Per Dwelling/Heat Pump in Balancing Services for Dutch dwelling with heat pump controlled through vendor's cloud platform
CS2-BL3-SN	SP-BL3	CP-SN	Maximum Annual Revenue Per Dwelling/Heat Pump in Balancing Services for Dutch dwelling with heat pump controlled through monitor and control device
CS2-BL4-SD	SP-BL4	CP-SD	Maximum Annual Revenue Per Dwelling/Heat Pump in Balancing Services for Dutch dwelling with heat pump controlled through vendor's cloud platform
CS2-BL4-SC	SP-BL4	CP-SC	Annual Savings of Barcelona low-insulation dwelling with just electric heaters (without heat pump)
CS2-BL5-SD	SP-BL5	CP-SD	Annual Savings of Barcelona low-insulation dwelling with electric heaters and PV (without heat pump)
CS2-BL5-SC	SP-BL5	CP-SC	Annual Savings of Barcelona low-insulation dwelling with electric heaters, PV and Battery (without heat pump)
CS2-BH1-SN	SP-BH1	CP-SN	Annual Savings of Barcelona low-insulation dwelling with heat pump and PV with heat pump controlled through monitor and control device
CS2-BH2-SN	SP-BH2	CP-SN	Annual Savings of Barcelona low-insulation dwelling with heat pump and PV with heat pump controlled through vendor's cloud platform
CS2-BH3-SN	SP-BH3	CP-SN	Annual Savings of Barcelona low-insulation dwelling with heat pump, PV and Battery with heat pump controlled through monitor and control device
CS2-BH4-SD	SP-BH4	CP-SD	Annual Savings of Barcelona low-insulation dwelling with heat pump, PV and Battery with

Id	Savings Profile	Cost Profile	Description
			heat pump controlled through vendor's cloud platform
CS2-BH4-SC	SP-BH4	CP-SC	Annual Savings of Barcelona high-insulation dwelling with just electric heaters (without heat pump)
CS2-BH5-SD	SP-BH5	CP-SD	Annual Savings of Barcelona high-insulation dwelling with electric heaters and PV (without heat pump)
CS2-BH5-SC	SP-BH5	CP-SC	Annual Savings of Barcelona high-insulation dwelling with electric heaters, PV and Battery (without heat pump)
CS2-ML1-SN	SP-ML1	CP-SN	Annual Savings of Barcelona high-insulation dwelling with heat pump and PV with heat pump controlled through monitor and control device
CS2-ML2-SN	SP-ML2	CP-SN	Annual Savings of Barcelona high-insulation dwelling with heat pump and PV with heat pump controlled through vendor's cloud platform
CS2-ML3-SN	SP-ML3	CP-SN	Annual Savings of Barcelona high-insulation dwelling with heat pump, PV and Battery with heat pump controlled through monitor and control device
CS2-ML4-SD	SP-ML4	CP-SD	Annual Savings of Barcelona high-insulation dwelling with heat pump, PV and Battery with heat pump controlled through vendor's cloud platform
CS2-ML4-SC	SP-ML4	CP-SC	Annual Savings of Madrid low-insulation dwelling with just electric heaters (without heat pump)
CS2-ML5-SD	SP-ML5	CP-SD	Annual Savings of Madrid low-insulation dwelling with electric heaters and PV (without heat pump)
CS2-ML5-SC	SP-ML5	CP-SC	Annual Savings of Madrid low-insulation dwelling with electric heaters, PV and Battery (without heat pump)
CS2-MH1-SN	SP-MH1	CP-SN	Annual Savings of Madrid low-insulation dwelling with heat pump and PV with heat pump controlled through monitor and control device

Id	Savings Profile	Cost Profile	Description
CS2-MH2-SN	SP-MH2	CP-SN	Annual Savings of Madrid low-insulation dwelling with heat pump and PV with heat pump controlled through vendor's cloud platform
CS2-MH3-SN	SP-MH3	CP-SN	Annual Savings of Madrid low-insulation dwelling with heat pump, PV and Battery with heat pump controlled through monitor and control device
CS2-MH4-SD	SP-MH4	CP-SD	Annual Savings of Madrid low-insulation dwelling with heat pump, PV and Battery with heat pump controlled through vendor's cloud platform
CS2-MH4-SC	SP-MH4	CP-SC	Annual Savings of Madrid high-insulation dwelling with just electric heaters (without heat pump)
CS2-MH5-SD	SP-MH5	CP-SD	Annual Savings of Madrid high-insulation dwelling with electric heaters and PV (without heat pump)
CS2-MH5-SC	SP-MH5	CP-SC	Annual Savings of Madrid high-insulation dwelling with electric heaters, PV and Battery (without heat pump)

5.4.1. Break-Even Time

Initially, we calculate the break-even time in years for the different scenarios, that is the amount of time in years required for the savings generated in each scenario to equal the applicable capital and operational costs.

Since, both costs and revenues/savings are analogous to the number of members adopting and exploiting the FLEXCoop Solution, the break-even time is calculated for 250 to 5000 prosumers/dwellings (Table 23). The intermediate calculation to reach the results in Table 23, are presented in Annex 2: Economic CBA Detailed Calculations (Table 41 and Table 42).

Table 23. Break-Even Time in Year Per Scenario and Number of Prosumers

Break-Even Time in Year Per Scenario and Number of Prosumers						
Scenario	250	500	750	1000	2000	5000
CS1-N1-DD	Not Viable	Not Viable	Not Viable	Not Viable	Not Viable	Not Viable
CS1-N1-DC	Not Viable	Not Viable	Not Viable	Not Viable	Not Viable	Not Viable

Break-Even Time in Year Per Scenario and Number of Prosumers						
Scenario	250	500	750	1000	2000	5000
CS1-N2-DD	15,26	10,38	9,36	8,92	8,33	8,01
CS1-N2-DC	23,82	12,63	10,89	10,19	9,28	8,80
CS2-BL1-SN	Not Viable					
CS2-BL2-SN	Not Viable					
CS2-BL3-SN	Not Viable	>25	>25	>25	24,33	21,84
CS2-BL4-SD	Not Viable					
CS2-BL4-SC	Not Viable					
CS2-BL5-SD	Not Viable					
CS2-BL5-SC	Not Viable					
CS2-BH1-SN	Not Viable	Not Viable	Not Viable	Not Viable	>25	>25
CS2-BH2-SN	Not Viable					
CS2-BH3-SN	Not Viable	Not Viable	>25	>25	>25	>25
CS2-BH4-SD	Not Viable					
CS2-BH4-SC	Not Viable					
CS2-BH5-SD	Not Viable					
CS2-BH5-SC	Not Viable					
CS2-ML1-SN	Not Viable					
CS2-ML2-SN	Not Viable					
CS2-ML3-SN	>25	19,62	16,30	15,03	13,44	12,63
CS2-ML4-SD	Not Viable					
CS2-ML4-SC	Not Viable					
CS2-ML5-SD	Not Viable					
CS2-ML5-SC	Not Viable					
CS2-MH1-SN	Not Viable	Not Viable	>25	>25	>25	>25
CS2-MH2-SN	Not Viable	Not Viable	Not Viable	Not Viable	>25	>25

Break-Even Time in Year Per Scenario and Number of Prosumers						
Scenario	250	500	750	1000	2000	5000
CS2-MH3-SN	>25	>25	21,36	19,23	16,71	15,49
CS2-MH4-SD	Not Viable					
CS2-MH4-SC	Not Viable					
CS2-MH5-SD	Not Viable					
CS2-MH5-SC	Not Viable					

There seems to be specific conditions under which a business case can be consider viable. It is clear that since the FLEXCoop Solution has an annual license fee per prosumer/member of 40€, any scenario with annual savings below 40€ is not viable. If we consider scenarios with heat pumps controlled through the vendor’s cloud platform, which has an additional annual fee of 25€, any such scenario with annual savings below 65€ is not viable.

There is also the FLEXCoop solution annual license of 12.000€ that has to be covered by annual savings per prosumer/member. This coverage depends on the number of prosumers/members. And there are also the dwelling initial capital costs that vary between 547€ and 789€ which represent considerable figures as there are costs who need at least a benefit of 79€ per year to cover these specific costs within seven (7) years.

5.4.1.1. Break-even time sensitivity under different FLEXCoop Solution pricing schemas

We can have some insights on the effect the pricing schema for the FLEXCoop solution has on the break-even time. To do so, we have to consider a specific scenario. We choose the best scenario, namely the CS1-N2-DD: “Maximum Annual Revenue Per Dwelling/Heat Pump in Balancing Services for Dutch dwelling with heat pump controlled through monitor and control device”. By defining a specific number of cooperative members, we can calculate the break-even time required per annual license fee for the FLEXCoop Solution and per annual license fee for members. The results are presented in Table 24.

The pricing schema used is the one in the orange cell (FLEXCoop Solution annual fee of 12.000€ plus an additional licence fee of 40€ per cooperative member). We can see in the green cells that there numerous pricing schemas with similar results. Moreover, it is evident that the break-even time is quite insensitive to small differences in the pricing schema.

For example, going from 40€ to 30€ for the additional annual license fee per cooperative member lowers the break-even time from 10,38 years to 9,18 years. Similarly, going from 40€ to 50€ for the additional annual license fee per cooperative member increases the break-even time from 10,38 years to 11,93 years. For the specific example, it means that a 25% decrease in the additional annual license fee per cooperative member has an 11,6 % decrease of the break-even time. A 25% increase in the additional annual license fee per cooperative member has an 14,9% increase of the break-even time. A 50% increase in the FLEXCoop Solution

annual license fee from 12.000€ to 18.000€ will result in a 18,4% increase of the break-even time (from 10,38 to 12,29 years).

Table 24. Break-even time (in years) sensitivity under different FLEXCoop Solution pricing schemas for 500 members in scenario CS1-N2-DD

	Platform Annual License Fee								
	10.000 €	12.000 €	15.000 €	18.000 €	20.000 €	22.000 €	25.000 €	28.000 €	30.000 €
20 €	7,91	8,24	8,78	9,40	9,86	10,38	11,25	12,29	13,10
22 €	8,07	8,41	8,98	9,63	10,11	10,65	11,58	12,68	13,54
25 €	8,32	8,68	9,29	9,99	10,51	11,10	12,11	13,32	14,27
28 €	8,59	8,98	9,63	10,38	10,95	11,58	12,68	14,02	15,08
30 €	8,78	9,18	9,86	10,65	11,25	11,93	13,10	14,53	15,67
32 €	8,98	9,40	10,11	10,95	11,58	12,29	13,54	15,08	16,31
35 €	9,29	9,74	10,51	11,41	12,11	12,89	14,27	15,98	17,37
38 €	9,63	10,11	10,95	11,93	12,68	13,54	15,08	17,00	18,58
40 €	9,86	10,38	11,25	12,29	13,10	14,02	15,67	17,76	19,49
42 €	10,11	10,65	11,58	12,68	13,54	14,53	16,31	18,58	20,49
45 €	10,51	11,10	12,11	13,32	14,27	15,37	17,37	19,98	22,19
48 €	10,95	11,58	12,68	14,02	15,08	16,31	18,58	21,59	24,21
50 €	11,25	11,93	13,10	14,53	15,67	17,00	19,49	22,83	25,77

Due to nature of the calculations involved (linear functions) we can safely assume that the break-even sensitivity displays the same pattern independently of number of cooperative members and scenario involved.

5.4.2. Savings to Break-Even in 7 Years with current cost profiles

The next step is to examine the parameters under which a FLEXCoop Solution deployment to a cooperative be consider viable. For this, we calculate the average annual revenues/savings per dwelling/prosumer in order to break-even in seven (7) years considering the current cost profiles identified in Table 19.

Table 25. Annual Dwelling Revenues/Savings Required to Break-Even in 7 Years Year Per Cost Profile and Number of Prosumers

		Annual Dwelling Revenues/Savings Required to Break-Even in 7 Years Per Cost Profile and Number of Prosumers					
Cost Profile	Description	250	500	750	1000	2000	5000
CP-DD	Cost Profile of Dutch dwelling with heat pump controlled through monitor and control device	203,57€	178,14€	169,67€	165,43€	159,07€	155,26€
CP-DC	Cost Profile of Dutch dwellings with heat pump controlled through vendor's cloud platform	208,29€	182,86€	174,38€	170,14€	163,79€	159,97€
CP-SN	Cost Profile of Spanish dwelling with electric heaters (without heat pump)	202,43€	177,00€	168,52€	164,29€	157,93€	154,11€
CP-SD	Cost Profile of Spanish dwellings with heat pump controlled through monitor and control device	189,29€	163,86€	155,38€	151,14€	144,79€	140,97€
CP-SC	Cost Profile of Spanish dwellings with heat pump controlled through vendor's cloud platform	194,00€	168,57€	160,10€	155,86€	149,50€	145,69€

Under current conditions, the bottom line is that, for a FLEXCoop Solution deployment to be considered viable (7 years to break-even) it should have at least 500 cooperative members and more than 160€ annual savings per dwelling/prosumer. For 250 cooperative members involved, there are required at least 189€ annual savings per dwelling/prosumer, while for 1.000 cooperative members the required annual savings per dwelling/prosumer are 151€. The situation does not change much by increasing the number of members. For 5.000 cooperative members there is still a minimum of 141€ required annual savings per dwelling/prosumer.

In comparison, the best actual savings profile, the SP-N2: Maximum Annual Revenue Per Dwelling/Heat Pump in Balancing Services for Dutch dwelling, exhibits 141€ estimated annual savings per dwelling/prosumer.

5.4.3. Dwellings Initial Capital Costs to Break-Even in 7 Years with estimated savings profiles

Considering the current savings profiles, that is the estimations of savings in The Netherlands and in Spain for the specific modelling presented in section 5.2, we can examine the estimated initial capital costs per dwelling that would make each scenario's profit-loss analysis to break-even in 7 years.

Table 26 presents the required initial capital costs per dwelling/prosumer required to break-even in 7 years per scenario and number of prosumers. Initial capital costs per dwelling/prosumer include the indicative BoM for the specific scenario as well the initial installation and customisation costs of the devices in the BoM.

Table 26. Dwelling Initial Capital Costs Required to Break-Even in 7 Years Per Scenario and Number of Prosumers

		Dwelling Initial Capital Costs Required to Break-Even in 7 Years Per Scenario and Number of Prosumers					
Scenario	Description	250	500	750	1000	2000	5000
CS1-N1-DD	Minimum Annual Revenue Per Dwelling/Heat Pump in Balancing Services for Dutch dwelling with heat pump controlled through monitor and control device	-	-	8 €	16 €	28 €	35 €
CS1-N1-DC	Minimum Annual Revenue Per Dwelling/Heat Pump in Balancing Services for Dutch dwelling with heat pump controlled through vendor's cloud platform	-	-	-	-	6 €	26 €
CS1-N2-DD	Maximum Annual Revenue Per Dwelling/Heat Pump in Balancing Services for Dutch dwelling with heat pump controlled through monitor and control device	671 €	356 €	250 €	198 €	119 €	72 €

		Dwelling Initial Capital Costs Required to Break-Even in 7 Years Per Scenario and Number of Prosumers					
Scenario	Description	250	500	750	1000	2000	5000
CS1-N2-DC	Maximum Annual Revenue Per Dwelling/Heat Pump in Balancing Services for Dutch dwelling with heat pump controlled through vendor's cloud platform	496 €	268 €	192 €	154 €	97 €	63 €
CS2-BL1-SN	Annual Savings of Barcelona low-insulation dwelling with just electric heater without heat pump	-	-	-	-	14 €	30 €
CS2-BL2-SN	Annual Savings of Barcelona low-insulation dwelling with electric heater with PV without heat pump	-	-	-	-	5 €	26 €
CS2-BL3-SN	Annual Savings of Barcelona low-insulation dwelling with electric heater with PV and Battery without heat pump	231 €	136 €	104 €	88 €	64 €	50 €
CS2-BL4-SD	Annual Savings of Barcelona low-insulation dwelling with heat pump with PV with heat pump controlled through monitor and control device	-	-	-	-	6 €	26 €
CS2-BL4-SC	Annual Savings of Barcelona low-insulation dwelling with heat pump with PV with heat pump controlled through vendor's cloud platform	-	-	-	-	-	18 €
CS2-BL5-SD	Annual Savings of Barcelona low-insulation dwelling with Heat pump with PV and Battery with heat pump controlled through monitor and control device	-	-	-	-	19 €	32 €
CS2-BL5-SC	Annual Savings of Barcelona low-insulation dwelling with Heat pump with PV and Battery with heat pump controlled through vendor's cloud platform	-	-	-	-	-	23 €
CS2-BH1-SN	Annual Savings of Barcelona high-insulation dwelling with just electric heater without heat pump	7 €	24 €	29 €	32 €	36 €	38 €
CS2-BH2-SN	Annual Savings of Barcelona high-insulation dwelling with electric heater with PV without heat pump	-	-	-	5 €	23 €	33 €

		Dwelling Initial Capital Costs Required to Break-Even in 7 Years Per Scenario and Number of Prosumers					
Scenario	Description	250	500	750	1000	2000	5000
CS2-BH3-SN	Annual Savings of Barcelona high-insulation dwelling with electric heater with PV and Battery without heat pump	107 €	73 €	62 €	57 €	48 €	43 €
CS2-BH4-SD	Annual Savings of Barcelona high-insulation dwelling with heat pump with PV with heat pump controlled through monitor and control device	-	-	-	-	1 €	25 €
CS2-BH4-SC	Annual Savings of Barcelona high-insulation dwelling with heat pump with PV with heat pump controlled through vendor's cloud platform	-	-	-	-	-	16 €
CS2-BH5-SD	Annual Savings of Barcelona high-insulation dwelling with Heat pump with PV and Battery with heat pump controlled through monitor and control device	-	-	-	-	2 €	25 €
CS2-BH5-SC	Annual Savings of Barcelona high-insulation dwelling with Heat pump with PV and Battery with heat pump controlled through vendor's cloud platform	-	-	-	-	-	16 €
CS2-ML1-SN	Annual Savings of Madrid low-insulation dwelling with just electric heater without heat pump	-	-	-	0 €	20 €	32 €
CS2-ML2-SN	Annual Savings of Madrid low-insulation dwelling with electric heater with PV without heat pump	-	-	-	-	12 €	29 €
CS2-ML3-SN	Annual Savings of Madrid low-insulation dwelling with electric heater with PV and Battery without heat pump	414 €	227 €	165 €	134 €	87 €	59 €
CS2-ML4-SD	Annual Savings of Madrid low-insulation dwelling with heat pump with PV with heat pump controlled through monitor and control device	-	-	-	-	4 €	25 €
CS2-ML4-SC	Annual Savings of Madrid low-insulation dwelling with heat pump with PV with heat pump	-	-	-	-	-	17 €

		Dwelling Initial Capital Costs Required to Break-Even in 7 Years Per Scenario and Number of Prosumers					
Scenario	Description	250	500	750	1000	2000	5000
	controlled through vendor's cloud platform						
CS2-ML5-SD	Annual Savings of Madrid low-insulation dwelling with Heat pump with PV and Battery with heat pump controlled through monitor and control device	-	-	9 €	17 €	28 €	35 €
CS2-ML5-SC	Annual Savings of Madrid low-insulation dwelling with Heat pump with PV and Battery with heat pump controlled through vendor's cloud platform	-	-	-	-	6 €	27 €
CS2-MH1-SN	Annual Savings of Madrid high-insulation dwelling with just electric heater without heat pump	132 €	86 €	71 €	63 €	52 €	45 €
CS2-MH2-SN	Annual Savings of Madrid high-insulation dwelling with electric heater with PV without heat pump	37 €	38 €	39 €	39 €	40 €	40 €
CS2-MH3-SN	Annual Savings of Madrid high-insulation dwelling with electric heater with PV and Battery without heat pump	334 €	187 €	138 €	114 €	77 €	55 €
CS2-MH4-SD	Annual Savings of Madrid high-insulation dwelling with heat pump with PV with heat pump controlled through monitor and control device	-	-	-	-	1 €	24 €
CS2-MH4-SC	Annual Savings of Madrid high-insulation dwelling with heat pump with PV with heat pump controlled through vendor's cloud platform	-	-	-	-	-	16 €
CS2-MH5-SD	Annual Savings of Madrid high-insulation dwelling with Heat pump with PV and Battery with heat pump controlled through monitor and control device	-	-	-	6 €	23 €	33 €
CS2-MH5-SC	Annual Savings of Madrid high-insulation dwelling with Heat pump with PV and Battery with heat pump controlled through vendor's cloud platform	-	-	-	-	1 €	24 €

5.4.4. Insights on Benefits of Hypothetical Case study with Low BoMs

Current required investments in the prosumers' dwellings (Table 19) can be considered quite large leading to non-viable scenarios for adopting the FLEXCoop Solution. In this section we provide insights on expected returns of potential investments when considering considerably lower cost profiles.

This is clearly referring to a hypothetical future case study where most of devices in dwelling incorporating advanced IoT technologies are interconnected and accessible through universal protocols.

5.4.4.1. Hypothetical Future BoMs and Cost Profiles

In this context, we outline 2 BoMs where a minimum number of auxiliary devices are required besides the OSB (BoM6) and no other device besides the OSB is required (BoM7). In these “future” BoMs, acquisition prices for all devices, including the OSB, is set to 80 € per device.

Table 27. BoM6 – Hypothetical indicative BoM for dwellings requiring a minimum number of auxiliary devices

INDICATIVE DEVICE NAME	INDICATIVE UNIT PRICE	QUANTITY	TOTAL PRICE
Power Metering			
Power Metering Device	80€	1	80€
HVAC System Control + Sensing			
Sensor and/or Control Device	80€	1	80€
DR Measurement			
OSB	80€	1	80€
<i>BoM Indicative Grand Total</i>			240€

Table 28. BoM7 - Hypothetical OSB-Only BoM

INDICATIVE DEVICE NAME	INDICATIVE UNIT PRICE	QUANTITY	TOTAL PRICE
<i>DR Measurement</i>			
OSB	80€	1	80€
<i>BoM Indicative Grand Total</i>			80€

Retaining the possibility of existence of HVAC devices requiring a subscription to access and control them in this hypothetical future case study, we identify the cost profiles presented in Table 29.

Table 29. Hypothetical future cost profiles

Id	Description	Applicable BoM	BoM Cost	BoM Installation Costs	Annual Subscription Cost	Total Dwelling Capital Costs	Total Dwelling Annual Costs
CP-MIN	Minimum BoM with heat pump controllable directly by OSB	BoM6	240€	0€	0€	240€	0€
CP-MINC	Minimum BoM with heat pump controlled through vendor's cloud platform	BoM6	240€	0€	25€	240€	25€
CP-OSB	Only-OSB BoM	BoM7	80€	0€	0€	80€	0€
CP-OSBC	Only-OSB BoM with heat pump controlled through vendor's cloud platform	BoM7	80€	0€	25€	80€	25€

5.4.4.2. Hypothetical Savings Profiles and Scenarios

To use the hypothetical cost profiles of the previous section, we create 5 indicative savings profiles ranging from 80€ to 200€ of annual revenues/savings per dwelling/prosumer as presented in Table 30.

Table 30. Hypothetical Annual Savings Profiles (From 80€ to 200€)

Id	Description	Annual Savings
SP-80	Annual savings of 80€ per dwelling/prosumer	80€
SP-100	Annual savings of 100€ per dwelling/prosumer	100€
SP-120	Annual savings of 120€ per dwelling/prosumer	120€

Id	Description	Annual Savings
SP-150	Annual savings of 150€ per dwelling/prosumer	150€
SP-200	Annual savings of 200€ per dwelling/prosumer	200€

By combining the savings profiles of Table 30 with all the cost profiles of Table 29 we create the set of different scenarios we can examine for the hypothetical future case study. The available scenarios are presented in Table 31.

Table 31. Set of different scenarios in the hypothetical future case study

Id	Savings Profile	Cost Profile	Description
CS3-80-MIN	SP-80	CP-MIN	Annual savings of 80€ per dwelling/prosumer and Low BoM with heat pump controllable directly by OSB
CS3-80-MINC	SP-80	CP-MINC	Annual savings of 80€ per dwelling/prosumer and Low Bom with heat pump controlled through vendor's cloud platform
CS3-80-OSB	SP-80	CP-OSB	Annual savings of 80€ per dwelling/prosumer and Only-OSB BoM
CS3-80-OSBC	SP-80	CP-OSBC	Annual savings of 80€ per dwelling/prosumer and Only-OSB BoM with heat pump controlled through vendor's cloud platform
CS3-100-MIN	SP-100	CP-MIN	Annual savings of 100€ per dwelling/prosumer and Low BoM with heat pump controllable directly by OSB
CS3-100-MINC	SP-100	CP-MINC	Annual savings of 100€ per dwelling/prosumer and Low Bom with heat pump controlled through vendor's cloud platform
CS3-100-OSB	SP-100	CP-OSB	Annual savings of 100€ per dwelling/prosumer and Only-OSB BoM
CS3-100-OSBC	SP-100	CP-OSBC	Annual savings of 100€ per dwelling/prosumer and Only-OSB BoM with heat pump controlled through vendor's cloud platform
CS3-120-MIN	SP-120	CP-MIN	Annual savings of 120€ per dwelling/prosumer and Low BoM with heat pump controllable directly by OSB

Id	Savings Profile	Cost Profile	Description
CS3-120-MINC	SP-120	CP-MINC	Annual savings of 120€ per dwelling/prosumer and Low BoM with heat pump controlled through vendor's cloud platform
CS3-120-OSB	SP-120	CP-OSB	Annual savings of 120€ per dwelling/prosumer and Only-OSB BoM
CS3-120-OSBC	SP-120	CP-OSBC	Annual savings of 120€ per dwelling/prosumer and Only-OSB BoM with heat pump controlled through vendor's cloud platform
CS3-150-MIN	SP-150	CP-MIN	Annual savings of 150€ per dwelling/prosumer and Low BoM with heat pump controllable directly by OSB
CS3-150-MINC	SP-150	CP-MINC	Annual savings of 150€ per dwelling/prosumer and Low BoM with heat pump controlled through vendor's cloud platform
CS3-150-OSB	SP-150	CP-OSB	Annual savings of 150€ per dwelling/prosumer and Only-OSB BoM
CS3-150-OSBC	SP-150	CP-OSBC	Annual savings of 150€ per dwelling/prosumer and Only-OSB BoM with heat pump controlled through vendor's cloud platform
CS3-200-MIN	SP-200	CP-MIN	Annual savings of 200€ per dwelling/prosumer and Low BoM with heat pump controllable directly by OSB
CS3-200-MINC	SP-200	CP-MINC	Annual savings of 200€ per dwelling/prosumer and Low BoM with heat pump controlled through vendor's cloud platform
CS3-200-OSB	SP-200	CP-OSB	Annual savings of 200€ per dwelling/prosumer and Only-OSB BoM
CS3-200-OSBC	SP-200	CP-OSBC	Annual savings of 200€ per dwelling/prosumer and Only-OSB BoM with heat pump controlled through vendor's cloud platform

5.4.4.3. Break-Even Time for Developed Hypothetical Future Scenarios

Table 32 presents the break-even time in years per hypothetical scenario and number of prosumers. The evident conclusion is that significantly lowering the initial capital costs in ICT

infrastructure within the dwellings and related installation and setup services, the break-even time in years is substantially lowered as well.

The key parameter is the expected savings per dwelling/prosumer. For expected savings per dwelling lower than 120€ is difficult to identify viable business cases. But even for such expected savings per dwelling, there are viable business cases (E.g. scenarios CS3-80-OSB and CS3-100-MIN which are breaking-even before the seven year mark starting from 450-500 cooperative members).

Break-even times are considerably higher for scenarios with heat pumps controlled through the vendors' platform. Starting from expected savings of 120€ and 500 cooperative members, low initial capital costs per dwellings yield very interesting business cases with break-even times lower than 3 years for most cases.

Table 32. Break-Even Time in Years Per Scenario and Number of Prosumers

Break-Even Time in Year Per Scenario and Number of Prosumers						
Scenario	250	500	750	1000	2000	5000
CS3-80-MIN	Not Viable	15,63	10,28	8,75	7,13	6,41
CS3-80-MINC	Not Viable	Not Viable	Not Viable	>25	>25	19,13
CS3-80-OSB	Not Viable	5,63	3,61	3,04	2,43	2,15
CS3-80-OSBC	Not Viable	Not Viable	Not Viable	>25	9,17	6,43
CS3-100-MIN	21,67	6,94	5,61	5,10	4,49	4,18
CS3-100-MINC	Not Viable	22,73	12,98	10,65	8,36	7,39
CS3-100-OSB	8,33	2,50	1,97	1,77	1,53	1,41
CS3-100-OSBC	Not Viable	8,18	4,56	3,70	2,84	2,48
CS3-120-MIN	8,13	4,46	3,85	3,60	3,28	3,11
CS3-120-MINC	>25	8,06	6,32	5,70	4,95	4,58
CS3-120-OSB	3,13	1,61	1,35	1,25	1,11	1,04
CS3-120-OSBC	14,29	2,90	2,22	1,98	1,68	1,54
CS3-150-MIN	4,19	2,91	2,62	2,50	2,33	2,24
CS3-150-MINC	7,03	4,10	3,57	3,36	3,07	2,92
CS3-150-OSB	1,61	1,05	0,92	0,87	0,79	0,75
CS3-150-OSBC	2,70	1,48	1,26	1,16	1,04	0,98

Break-Even Time in Year Per Scenario and Number of Prosumers						
Scenario	250	500	750	1000	2000	5000
CS3-200-MIN	2,32	1,84	1,71	1,66	1,57	1,53
CS3-200-MINC	2,99	2,25	2,07	1,99	1,88	1,82
CS3-200-OSB	0,89	0,66	0,60	0,57	0,54	0,51
CS3-200-OSBC	1,15	0,81	0,73	0,69	0,64	0,61

5.4.4.4. Savings to Break-Even in 7 Years

To complete the exploration of expected results for low initial capital costs per dwellings, the average annual revenues/savings per dwelling/prosumer in order to break-even in seven (7) years considering the hypothetical cost profiles identified in Table 29 are presented in Table 33.

Table 33. Annual Dwelling Revenues/Savings Required to Break-Even in 7 Years Year Per Hypothetical Scenario and Number of Prosumers

Annual Dwelling Revenues/Savings Required to Break-Even in 7 Years Year Per Hypothetical Scenario and Number of Prosumers							
Cost Profile	Description	250	500	750	1000	2000	5000
CP-MIN	Low BoM with heat pump controllable directly by OSB	125,14€	99,71€	91,24€	87,00€	80,64€	76,83€
CP-MINC	Low Bom with heat pump controlled through vendor's cloud platform	150,14€	124,71€	116,24€	112,00€	105,64€	101,83€
CP-OSB	Only-OSB BoM	102,29€	76,86€	68,38€	64,14€	57,79€	53,97€
CP-OSBC	Only-OSB BoM with heat pump controlled through vendor's cloud platform	127,29€	101,86€	93,38€	89,14€	82,79€	78,97€

5.5. Conclusions

The data analysis from the case studies in the Netherlands and Spain, converge in the conclusion that current cost of the BoM and installation and customisation services per dwelling (in conjunction with the FLEXCoop Solution pricing scheme) required to deploy the FLEXCoop Solution to the prosumers is considerably high. These costs require expected savings of more than 160€ annual savings per dwelling/prosumer and cooperatives with at least 500 members using the FLEXCoop Solution.

The number of prosumers adopting the FLEXCoop Solution per cooperative is important, as, at the moment, there is no business case for cooperatives having less than 200-250 prosumers using the solution. Lowering the initial capital costs per dwelling show some interesting scenarios in terms of viability and should be a key focus point for the future.

For particular services, e.g. balancing services, where current regulation across Europe requires a minimum bid of one MW for participation, it may even require a few thousands prosumers.

There are two main developments that can remedy substantially the expected benefits for cooperatives (aggregators) and their members:

- Regulatory conformity throughout Europe,
- Development, standardisation and utilisation of common open communication and control protocol for devices and platforms/solutions.

Common regulations will enable the deployment of the FLEXCoop Solution in conditions where more than one optimisation strategy is concurrently exploitable. In this sense, the same investments will be able to create benefits for the involved stakeholders (cooperatives/aggregators and prosumers) from two or more sources.

HVAC device vendors are offering their own services for controlling and exploiting the potential of their devices by consumers. This kind of services are in direct competition with the FLEXCoop Solution. The distinctive difference is that while FLEXCoop is moving the underlying market sector towards democratisation, vendors' platform is restricting prosumers to the vendors' own ecosystem of devices and services. The adoption of open standards is crucial in lowering the investment required to adopt solutions like FLEXCoop and in consequence allowing cooperatives/aggregators and their members to play a leading role in the energy market and achieve the energy transition.

In this context, cooperatives are encouraged to explore partnerships with HVAC device vendors and create dedicated R&D units for data analysis, modelling of business cases and simulation execution. The key point is the data acquisition and data governance. Cooperatives should deploy solutions that allow them to have full ownership and digital sovereignty over the data and, if possible, have control and ownership (exclusive or shared) of the related algorithms.

6. ENVIRONMENTAL & SOCIAL COST-BENEFIT ANALYSIS

In FLEXCoop deliverable D7.2 – *FLEXCoop Evaluation Framework and Respective Validation Scenarios*, FLEXCoop overall environmental impacts have been reviewed using Kate Raworth's "sustainability doughnut" [24]. Out of the numerous positive and negative

environmental impacts of the FLEXCoop solution, only a sub-selection was retained to be assessed.

Related to the more environmental aspects: the CO₂ savings through FLEXCoop will be calculated, together with the CO₂ impact of FLEXCoop as an ICT solution.

The social aspects of things will be studied “live” with a set of questions to end-users aiming at defining how they have received the project and if the expected social impacts of the solution are perceived as such by the users.

6.1. Environmental CBA

Environmental CBAs will look in priority at CO₂ impact, ignoring the other aspects of this issue (impact on land, water, biodiversity, etc.). First, we will look at the CO₂ reduction (benefits) potential for FLEXCoop activities according to the different business cases being implemented in our two pilots, and then examine the CO₂ emissions (costs) induced by the FLEXCoop solution itself.

6.1.1. CO₂ savings

There are 3 implemented business cases in the project. For each of them the calculation of CO₂ savings appears different.

6.1.1.1. Participation into balancing services

as in the In the Dutch pilot, demand-side flexibility will be used to participate in aFRR market (secondary reserves).

FLEXCoop makes it possible to shift loads over time in households. If the energy system is not balanced there can be two situations. In both situations there is a request for balancing services like secondary reserve. (i) There is too much power in the market. Traditional solution is that the fossil fuel plant stops producing energy which will have a negative impact on CO₂ emissions. FLEXCoop solution makes households shift their loads and start using more energy which has less impact on CO₂ emissions. The assumption is that the energy usage in households in total will not change. (ii) There is too little power in the market. Traditional solution is that the fossil fuel plant start producing energy which will have a positive impact on CO₂ emissions. To facilitate the calculation, only the first case will be assessed.

Considering the case where households shift their loads and stop using energy, which has less impact on CO₂ emission, **CO₂ savings** in this case correspond to the CO₂ emissions of the same services provided by conventional generation, minus the CO₂ emission of the demand-side flexibility unit which would be close to zero.

In section 4 the range of value to provide a 1 MW bid in the aFRR mechanism, is a portfolio of 250 to 5000 houses each delivering from 453 kWh (“evenly strategy”) to 811 kWh (“concentrate strategy”) up regulation a year.

1 house up regulation / y. (kWh)	Same service provided with gas generation (490g CO₂eq/kWh¹)
453	453 x 490 = 221 970
811	811 x 490 = 397 390

The range of savings is between 221 kg and 397 kg CO₂ a year per households. This does not account for the savings related to the additional RES resources that may be integrated through additional flexibility.

6.1.1.2. Wholesale market sourcing optimisation

In the Spanish pilot, Demand-side flexibility will be used to purchase electricity at cheaper times in the day ahead market. Playing with assumptions, it could be forecasted that in a near future, the cheapest hours will match hours of renewable energy generation which correspond to assets with important capital expenditures, but low operational expenditures. Kenneth Leerbeck *et al.* [29] have found out that by using heat pumps according CO₂ emission intensity forecasts savings could go up to 17%.

	Floor		Radiator	
	BC₁₉₇₇	BC_{2015:2018}	BC₁₉₇₇	BC_{2015:2018}
Family house				
Min. savings	0.5%	9.4%	1.8%	9.9%
Max. savings	2.7%	17.4%	2.8%	12.4%
Office building				
Min. savings	1.4%	7.8%	2.4%	8.1%
Max. savings	9.2%	16.0%	4.1%	12.3%

* Optimal concrete thickness of 50 mm. ** Optimal concrete thickness of 80 mm.

Table: Minimum and maximum savings using heat pumps piloting based on CO₂ emission intensity forecasts depending on Building Codes applied standards in Leerbeck *et al.* experimentation

However, the range of CO₂ savings is broad from between 0.5% and 2.7% for badly insulated buildings (built before 1977), to 2.8% and 12.4% for recent buildings but using radiator-heating. Based on the hope to see a renovation wave in Europe massively improving insulation in a near future, we will use an average of minimum and maximum values the best insulation standards in the residential sector (“family houses”). Therefore, the CO₂ savings may be 13.4% for houses

¹ Value from IPCC, 2014 quoted by ElectricityMap.org

using floor heating and 11.15% for houses with radiators. Nevertheless, a series of differences exists between this case and the pilot situation: the weather conditions are different and the dominating technologies in the energy mix may be different as well.

6.1.1.3. Self-consumption optimisation

In the Spanish pilot, demand-side flexibility from end-users equipped with solar PV panels will be used to increase the amount of self-generated electricity which is consumed within the house, the remaining possibility to shift load within this context would be used to optimise price as above.

CO₂ savings can be compared with the study by Kenneth Leerbeck *et al* made in Denmark on the bases of CO₂ forecasts. Though the reference energy in Denmark would be wind rather than solar, this gives an order of magnitude of available “flexibility” at household level to adapt to changing generation patterns. Therefore, as above, we may conclude that the CO₂ savings may be 13.4% for houses using floor heating and 11.15% for houses with radiators with the same precautions already mentioned

Calculation at system level holds significant difficulties as self-generated energy that goes into the grid will be consumed somewhere else. This requires deeper understanding of the limit of the system, but holds an interesting debate on the limits of generalised self-consumption.

6.1.2. CO₂ impact of the FLEXCoop IT architecture

6.1.2.1. Introduction and methodology

The gains in productivity and the new services offered by the so-called digitally enabled *dematerialisation* of the economy should not hide the growing energy consumption of the digital sector itself. In a recent report [5], the Think Tank “the Shift Project” describes this trend using the two graphs below.

The evolution of the digital sector’s consumption as a share of global consumption illustrates the growing issue it may represent. In particular, it is noticeable that the updated expected scenario (purple) is getting significantly closer to the worst-case scenario (red), towards an exponential development of ICT energy needs.

This second graph shows that while the use of the ICT infrastructure represents 55% of the sector’s energy consumption, the production and the renewal of ICT devices represents 45% of the consumed energy. FLEXCoop uses the overall digital infrastructure and has a contribution to its overall consumption. The table below describes FLEXCoop’s impact in each of the listed categories and provides an assessment of how difficult it is to calculate this impact.

Table 34. Overview of the different types of FLEXCoop energy consumption impact

Source of digital energy consumption	FLEXCoop energy consumption impact	Can we calculate it?
(i) Infrastructure		
Data centre use	GB space needed for installing and running FLEXCoop Software	Achievable
Network use	Data flows between the different FLEXCoop modules;	Achievable
Terminal Use	Terminal uses by all actors: marketplace manager; aggregators and end-users.	Too complex
	Consumption of dedicated device: OSBs + clamps and sensors	Achievable
(ii) Devices		
	Share of the incentive FLEXCoop represents in the acquisition and the use of ICT devices (esp. smart	Too complex

Computers, Smartphones and other devices production	phone)	
	Production of dedicated device	Too complex

Chosen approach. It is important to consider to what extent FLEXCoop, while it intends to participate in solving our energy challenges, does its maximum not to participate in a growing energy issue. However, considering the overall ICT infrastructure, most of the energy consumption uses remain too complex to be calculated. In this context, we will:

- focus on calculable items and calculate (i) how much capacity (GB) does FLEXCoop need and how much would it need to run at a commercial scale and (ii) the energy consumption of OSBs.
- issue recommendations to limit the CO2 impact of FLEXCoop in all these categories

6.1.2.2. FLEXCoop data centre energy use

In this section we will review (independently from the chosen hosting solution of each partner: internal or external server) the digital capacity (GB) needed to install and use FLEXCoop:

- (i) as of now (20 users) and
- (ii) at an early commercial stage (10K users).

Components per partners:

- Hypertech: Demand flexibility profiling and Flexibility forecasting, segmentation and aggregation
- ETRA: Aggregator toolkit, Local Demand Manager, Global Demand Manager, DR Settlement and Remuneration Module
- Fraunhofer: Open marketplace; DER registry
- Suite5: Prosumer Portal
- CIMNE: Middleware; District DER system;
- KONCAR: DER management system.

The table below describes the storage capacity needed for each module of the solution for 20 users and 10.000 users.

Table 35. Needed server capacity (GB) for Partners’ related modules and corresponding yearly energy consumption

Partner	Needed server capacity			
	... for 20 users		...for 10K users	
Hypertech	20GB	(1200 x 1.8) = 2,160 kWh/ year	500GB	(1200 x 1.8) = 2,160 kWh/year
ETRA	10 GB	1,230 kWh	10 GB	1,230 kWh/ year
Fraunhofer	0.01 GB	1000 kWh/ year	0.01 GB	1000 kWh/ year
Suite5	1 server	(1000 x 1.6) = 1,600 kWh/ year	1 server	(1000 x 1.6))= 1,600 kWh/ year
CIMNE	1 server	2,160 kWh / year	6 servers	6 x 2,160 kWh/ year
KONCAR	1 server	2,160 kWh / year	1 server	2,160 kWh kWh/ year
Total	9770 kWh		20 570 kWh	

The calculation holds an important gap in the difficulty to calculate not only storage-related energy, but processing-related energy. Moreover, the scaling up of data centre energy is not linear and the related FLEXCoop infrastructure for 20 users is almost the same than for 10 K users. Only the middleware requires more resources.

6.1.2.3. Data flow related to FLEXCoop functioning

The middleware is by definition the “hub” which centralises the flow of data through the FLEXCoop solution.

45GB of data has been transferred through the middleware in 10 months for 20 users. Moreover, Chris Adams [6] put online a simple calculation tool to assess the emissions from the use of networks and servers of average internet use. This methodology may be helpful for the final calculation.

Based on this information we can conclude the information in the table below.

	Yearly data flow	Related energy consumption
20 users	54 GB	127 kWh
10 K users	27 000 GB	63 418 kWh

6.1.2.4. FLEXCoop OSB energy use and CO2 impact

The OSB is the main FLEXCoop hardware device. Its main component is a Raspberry PI 3 Model B+ with a DC power input 5V/2.5A i.e. 12.5W (see D4.1 “FLEXCoop OSB Prototype Design” for more details. Thus, we can easily calculate its annual energy consumption to 109.5kWh.

Based on this figure we can simply multiply to assess the consumption of the OSB.

Table 36. kWh consumption of the OSB

	Yearly consumption of the OSB
1 user	109.5 kWh
20 users	2 190 kWh
10 000 users	1 095 000 kWh

6.1.2.5. Conclusion: Calculable emission of FLEXCoop ICT

The table below summarises the findings of the 3 above sections.

Table 37. Overview of FLEXCoop energy consumption (kWh/y)

Infrastructure	FLEXCoop impact	Results (kWh/y) (20 users)	Results (kWh/y) (10K users)
Data centre use	Kwh needed for storing FLEXCoop software	9770	20 570
Network use	Data flows between the different FLEXCoop modules; Data flows between prosumers portal and the solution.	127	63 418
Terminal Use	Terminal uses by all actors: marketplace manager; aggregators and end-users.	<i>Too complex</i>	<i>Too complex</i>
	Consumption of dedicated devices (OSBs)	2 190	1 095 000
Devices: Computers, Smartphones and others devices <u>production</u>	Share of the incentive FLEXCoop represents in the acquisition and the use of ICT devices (esp. smart phone)	<i>Too complex</i>	<i>Too complex</i>

Infrastructure	FLEXCoop impact	Results (kWh/y) (20 users)	Results (kWh/y) (10K users)
Total		12 087	1 178 988

Table 38. Summary of FLEXCoop tools energy use and related share per item

	20 users		10K users	
	kWh	%	kWh	%
Data centres	9,770	80.8%	20,570	1.7%
Network use	127	1.1%	63,418	5.4%
Home device use (OSB)	2,190	18.1%	1,095,000	92.9%
Total	12,087	100 %	1,178,988	100 %
Energy per user	604		118	

It is notable that, at its current scale, the main source of energy use (among the calculated ones) are the data centres (80%). However, as FLEXCoop would scale up, most of the current data centre infrastructure would still be adapted. Therefore, the main item which does not benefit from gain of scales are smart boxes in individual homes which represent the vast majority of FLEXCoop calculated energy consumption for 10 000 users (92%). Another consequence is that the energy consumption from the whole ICT infrastructure quickly decreases between 20 and 10K users, the OSB representing the only incompressible energy use.

From kWh to CO₂ emissions. The British company RENsmart [7] gathered data from the European Environmental Agency to provide an overview of the CO₂ emission per kWh depending on the national energy mix.

Table 39. CO₂(eq) emissions due to electricity generation per EU country

Country	kg CO ₂ per kWh
Sweden	0.013
Lithuania	0.018
France	0.059
Austria	0.085
Latvia	0.105
Finland	0.113
Slovakia	0.132
Denmark	0.166
Belgium	0.17
Croatia	0.21
Luxembourg	0.219
Slovenia	0.254
Italy	0.256
Hungary	0.26
Spain	0.265
United Kingdom	0.281
European Union (current composition)	0.296
Romania	0.306
Portugal	0.325
Ireland	0.425
Germany	0.441
Bulgaria	0.47
Netherlands	0.505
Czechia	0.513
Greece	0.623
Malta	0.648
Cyprus	0.677
Poland	0.773
Estonia	0.819

Using these values, the outcome in terms of energy consumption for 10 000 users would largely differ depending on the carbon intensity of the concerned country's energy mix.

Table 40. FLEXCoop tools CO₂(eq) emissions using different electricity mixes

	kg CO ₂ per kWh	Related CO ₂ emissions for 10K FLEXCoop users (kg of CO ₂)
Sweden	0.013	15 326.84
Spain	0.265	31 2431.8
Netherlands	0.505	595 388.9
Estonia	0.819	965 591.2
EU average	0.296	348 980.4

Solutions like FLEXCoop consumes electricity and the related CO₂ emissions depends a lot on the energy mix of the related country. In EU average this would represent 34 kg of CO₂ per year and per user (for a scaled-up solution).

6.1.2.6. Conclusion and recommendations to limit FLEXCoop CO₂ impact

To conclude the environmental CBA, the section highlights the main results together with some recommendations to limit CO₂ impact.

Overview of the main social and environmental CBA results

Taking into account that the contribution from a house participating into balancing reserves is between 453 and 811 kWh, representing 134 to 240kg of savings (EU average mix CO₂ emissions). The 34 kg of CO₂ mentioned above remain very much below these values.

Taking into account that the average consumption of a Spanish household is 3 500 kWh a year (representing 1 036 kg of CO₂ in EU average), FLEXCoop tools overall consumption (118 kWh) would represent only 3% of the household yearly consumption, which remains very much below the 11% to 13% CO₂ savings enabled through wholesale market sourcing CO₂ optimisation or self-consumption optimisation. The above mentions calculations hold a lot of approximations and would require a lot further enquiries to adjust the results.

Nevertheless, the order of magnitude presented are positive and can comfort the positive impact of FLEXCoop in terms of CO₂ savings.

Recommendations

Here is a short list of how FLEXCoop can be better designed and used to minimise its impact.

Data centre use. ‘How to reduce the GB of storage needed?’

- Privilege light software systems, weight the need for new features.
- Minimise databases to the strict minimum, avoid redundancies.
- Perform maintenance and upgrading of the software

Network use. ‘How to minimise the flow of data?’

- Integrate all FLEXCoop modules in a single server
- Assess the need for embedded storage within the OSB
- Locate servers as close as possible to the users

Terminal use. ‘How to minimise the energy needed by FLEXCoop user devices?’

- Avoid energy consuming app
- Take energy efficiency into account in the design of the OSB

Devices production (Computers, Smartphones and others). ‘How to reduce the energy needed to produce FLEXCoop required devices?’

- Privilege low-resource consuming software (in order to be compatible with the simplest devices)

6.2. Social CBA (End-user feedback)

In the previous deliverable FLEXCoop social impact had been listed using the Sustainability Doughnuts criteria as in the following list.

Energy:	(+) Cheaper energy (customer level) (+) Broader choice of energy services (customer level) (+) More resilient energy system through multiplication of local level energy actors (prosumers, cooperative aggregators)
Health:	(+) Less air pollution (society) (decrease of fossil fuel combustion related emissions) (+) Air quality control (customer level)
Income and work:	(+) Additional income through DR activities (customer level) (+) New set of non-relocatable jobs (society). (-) Loss of jobs in conventional energy sector (society)
Political voice:	(+) Cooperatives acting as citizens intermediary in energy policies and markets
Social equity:	(+) Decentralisation of energy markets revenues
Networks (resilience):	(+) Cooperatives connecting and empowering citizens (collective level) (+) More resilient communities (society level)

However, FLEXCoop provides a unique opportunity to ask directly the pilot end-users, who would have experimented with the services by the end of the project, what their appreciation of the services and their usefulness is.

In that perspective a questionnaire will be addressed to them tackling the following aspects:

- Participation into FLEXCoop Project
 - Preparation
 - Operational phase
- Expected longer-term services
 - Motivation (trigger)
 - Service model
 - Privacy.

The detailed questionnaire is available in Annex1.

7. CONCLUSIONS

In the presented text the results of many activities in the FLEXCoop project have been reported. In the first part the evaluation of solar power forecasts and experimental tests were presented. In the second part the economic and environment CBA were presented. For each section a conclusion was included in the end, so the conclusion below is a summary of the most important points of these.

In Section 2 the solar power forecast evaluation is presented. The solar power forecasts were calculated with an Open Source package which was partly developed in the FLEXCoop project. The forecast performance was evaluated with the developed solar power forecasting evaluation software, which can be used for continuously monitoring and evaluation of forecasts. Observations and NWP are input to the software, which then generates reports that can be used for understanding the quality of data and performance of the forecasting. An evaluation was carried out and presented separately for both an individual system and for all the 13 PV systems included in the project. The general conclusion is, that the applied forecast models work robustly and deliver a satisfactory forecast quality, with a level of error between 10% to 20% NRMSE (normalized with the max observed power). Finally, further improvements could be achieved by using better NWPs as input to the models.

In Section 3 the developed model for simulation of a building with a heat pump is presented. It can be used for flexibility assessment and through simulation for calculating revenue potential in various cases – as used in the economic CBA for calculating potential revenue for a building with a heat pump delivering balancing power on the Dutch aFRR market.

In Section 4 the evaluation of the experimental tests of the FLEXCoop is presented. Both the Dutch aFRR and Spanish self-optimisation cases are evaluated. The analysed data from the aFRR tests clearly indicates that the models behind the baseline calculation and subsequent control works as intended in several tests. However, it's also clear that in many cases the baseline cannot be followed and temperatures can exceed the comfort bounds, which is not unexpected given that the predictions have a 10 to 34 hours horizon. This leads to the learning

that this kind of control should focus on a shorter horizon and be frequently updated - which also is possible in the Dutch aFRR market, where so called “free bids” can be given all the way up to one hour before operation. In this way much more of the flexibility can be exploited, both because predictions become more accurate, but mostly because the available flexibility can be focused to the next few hours and doesn’t have to be “spread out” over 24 hours. Finally, the MPC model was tested and it’s clear that further development is required before the control and optimisation is functioning satisfactorily.

In sections 5 & 6, the CBA is presented. It’s an analysis has been conducted to evaluate the potential economic, social and environmental benefits of the FLEXCoop solution in the two cases studies, that is the Dutch and Spanish pilot sites. In both cases buildings and heating systems were simulated to obtain the potential revenue in the different scenarios. For the Dutch aFRR case the model outlined in Section 3 was applied. A potential revenue in the range between 37 and 141 EUR per year for an average residence was calculated. For the Spanish self-optimisation case a new model and its associated MPC optimisation was described, and how it was used with data from 2019 to obtain the potential benefits (savings) for different system components and climates.

Generally, the conclusion is that there is a benefit from applying optimisation in all cases, however there are big differences in the potential. The findings are that the relative savings (percentage difference) are high with a HP compared to an electric heater, simply because the total consumption is much lower with the HP (results in section 5.2.5.3). In absolute revenue only a low potential is available with low insulation level, it’s higher with high insulation, however with a battery the revenue potential increases considerable in all cases. In general, it must be taken into account that the results are based on the particular prices of 2019 (with 2021 tariff scheme) – thus in a future with more volatile prices due higher shares of renewables the economic potential of applying MPC can increase. Furthermore, we find that it is very important to take into account the properties of the buildings, where MPC is rolled out. Such that well insulated buildings are preferred, or some energy storage solution is available. Batteries are very expensive today, so other heat storage solutions should be explored (water tanks (although not so efficient with heat pumps) or phase change materials).

There is a need to further studies, where similar types of simulations are carried out. It would be highly relevant to use advanced building simulation software, such that the impact of model deficiencies is minimized. This should be carried out in combination with experiments in real representative building in order to verify the simulation results.

The economic cost-benefit analysis from the case studies in the Netherlands and Spain, converge in the conclusion that current cost of the BoMs and installation and customisation services per dwelling (in conjunction with the FLEXCoop Solution pricing scheme) required to deploy the FLEXCoop Solution to the prosumers is considerably high. These costs require expected savings of more than 160€ annual savings per dwelling/prosumer and cooperatives with at least 500 members using the FLEXCoop Solution.

The number of prosumers adopting the FLEXCoop Solution per cooperative is important, as, at the moment, there is no business case for cooperatives having less than 200-250 prosumers using the solution. Lowering the initial capital costs per dwelling show some interesting scenarios in terms of viability and should be a key focus point for the future.

There are two main developments that can remedy substantially the expected benefits for cooperatives (aggregators) and their members:

- Regulatory conformity throughout Europe, to enable the deployment of the FLEXCoop Solution in conditions where more than one optimisation strategy is concurrently exploitable.
- Development, standardisation and utilisation of common open communication and control protocol for devices and platforms/solutions to significantly lower initial capital costs per dwelling.

Regardless of specific market trends, cooperatives are encouraged to explore partnerships with HVAC device vendors and create dedicated R&D units for data analysis, modelling of business cases and simulation execution. The key point is the data acquisition and data governance [33]. Cooperatives should deploy solutions that allows them to have full “digital sovereignty”² [34] [35] as defined by the International Data Spaces Association (IDSA) and control over the data and, if possible, have control and ownership (exclusive or shared) of the related algorithms.

This will allow cooperatives to better monitor and understand market condition and status, evaluate business cases and outline the desired functionality. The final objective is to identify the services that can maximise profit while enforcing the necessary environmental-friendly strategies. Digital sovereignty can potentially create further data-related business models in the energy domain through the commercial exploitation of anonymised usage data sets or the participation in the development of the EU’s energy data spaces [36] in the future industrial ecosystem as addressed in the FLEXCoop deliverable D8.11 on “Policy/Market Reform Recommendations Report – Final Version [37].

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² According to IDSA digital sovereignty is the ability of a natural or legal person to exclusively and sovereignly decide concerning the usage of data as an economic asset.

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ANNEX 1: QUESTIONS TO END-USERS

The following questionnaire gathers the questions that will be asked to pilot end-users in the last workshop at the end of the project, and is aiming at understanding (i) how they've received the project? (ii) How would they welcome such a solution in the future?

Intro

Throughout the past month you have taken part within the FLEXCoop pilot where you have been experimenting the following services: Electricity monitoring, Device control, Appliance automation to receive extra-services/ payment (NL), ... to receive cheaper bills (ES); ... to increase self-consumption (ES).

Please provide us with some feedback on your experience.

Part 1: Participation into FLEXCoop Project

Preparation

1. How was the end-users' selection process carried out?
 - Good
 - Satisfactory
 - Bad
 - Additional comments: ...

2. How was the installation of the FLEXCoop solution performed?
 - Good
 - Satisfactory
 - Bad
 - Additional comments: ...

3. Did you have problems with the installed devices after the deployment?
 - No problem
 - Small problems quickly solved
 - Significant issues affecting my equipment normal functioning
 - Additional comments: ...

Operational phase

4. How did the relationship with the responsible cooperative go during the running of the project?
 - Good
 - Satisfactory
 - Bad

- What could be improved? : ...
5. What do you think about the Prosumer App?
- Good
 - Satisfactory
 - Bad
 - What could be improved or which functionality could be added? : ...

Overall

6. Do you think the flexibility tools of FLEXCoop are useful?
- Yes, they are important for the energy transition
 - Maybe, they could be useful
 - No, such tools are a distraction
7. Would you advise your neighbours and friends to use flexibility tools like the ones of FLEXCoop ?
- Yes
 - No
8. Did you find it interesting to participate in FLEXCoop?
- Yes, I've learnt interesting things
 - Not really, but I hope my participation have helped my cooperative
 - No, it was a complete loss of time
 - Additional comments: ...
9. Would you like to participate in a similar project in the near future?
- yes/no?

Part 2: Future flexibility services

Motivation

10. Do flexibility services seem interesting for you in the future?
- Yes, if you have a good service to offer, I'd subscribe
 - Maybe, I need to be further convinced
 - No, this kind of service is not for me
 - Additional comments: ...

11. What would be your key motivation to adopt it (please rank your priorities from 1 (high) to 6 (low))?

- It's easy (nr. ... priority)
- It's fun (nr. ... priority)
- It offers savings or revenues (nr. ... priority)
- It helps the energy transition (nr. ... priority)
- It helps my cooperative (nr. ... priority)
- It supports my energy autonomy through self-consumption (nr. ... priority)

Service model

12. Installing flexibility tools require some resources...Which model do you prefer?

- you pay for hardware and installation costs at the beginning, but the service is for free?
- Or you prefer no upfront cost, but have to pay a monthly fee?

13. What seems more interesting for you:

- to save electricity by consuming more from my own roof-top PV electricity
- to pay cheaper electricity by consuming more when prices are low
- To consume greener electricity by consuming more when renewables are feeding the system
- to get paid to contribute to system stability

14. If you would have to invest in the FLEXCoop solution. What payback time for your solution would you find acceptable:

- 1 to 3 years
- 3 to 5 years
- 5 to 8 years

Privacy

15. Are you worried about the privacy of your personal and electricity data?

- Yes, electricity data tells a lot
- No, who cares about electricity data?

16. If yes, what measure seems more effective to protect your rights?

- The fact that my co-op is in charge is already reassuring for me.
- I want to know clearly who has access, to which data and what for.
- I want to be informed regularly on the use of my private data.

ANNEX 2: ECONOMIC CBA DETAILED CALCULATIONS

Table 41. Detailed economic CBA calculations of break-even times per scenario and number of cooperative members (250,500,750)

Scenario	Solution Initial Capital Costs	Number of cooperative members											
		250				500				750			
		Dwellings Initial Capital Costs	Dwellings Annual Operational Costs	Solution Annual Operational Costs	Break Even Time	Dwellings Initial Capital Costs	Dwellings Annual Operational Costs	Solution Annual Operational Costs	Break Even Time	Dwellings Initial Capital Costs	Dwellings Annual Operational Costs	Solution Annual Operational Costs	Break Even Time
CS1-N1-DD	5.000 €	197.250 €	0 €	22.000 €	-15,86	394.500 €	0 €	32.000 €	-29,59	591.750 €	0 €	42.000 €	-41,88
CS1-N1-DC		161.750 €	6.250 €		-8,78	323.500 €	12.500 €		-12,63	485.250 €	18.750 €		-14,86
CS1-N2-DD		197.250 €	0 €		15,26	394.500 €	0 €		10,38	591.750 €	0 €		9,36
CS1-N2-DC		161.750 €	6.250 €		23,82	323.500 €	12.500 €		12,63	485.250 €	18.750 €		10,89
CS2-BL1-SN		195.250 €	0 €		-11,97	390.500 €	0 €		-18,44	585.750 €	0 €		-22,58
CS2-BL2-SN		195.250 €	0 €		-10,36	390.500 €	0 €		-14,84	585.750 €	0 €		-17,39
CS2-BL3-SN		195.250 €	0 €		-81,73	390.500 €	0 €		55,70	585.750 €	0 €		35,48
CS2-BL4-SD		172.250 €	0 €		-9,33	344.500 €	0 €		-13,44	516.750 €	0 €		-15,81
CS2-BL4-SC		136.750 €	6.250 €		-5,61	273.500 €	12.500 €		-7,23	410.250 €	18.750 €		-8,03
CS2-BL5-SD		172.250 €	0 €		-11,65	344.500 €	0 €		-18,96	516.750 €	0 €		-24,10
CS2-BL5-SC		136.750 €	6.250 €		-6,60	273.500 €	12.500 €		-9,00	410.250 €	18.750 €		-10,28
CS2-BH1-SN		195.250 €	0 €		-19,15	390.500 €	0 €		-44,36	585.750 €	0 €		-80,13
CS2-BH2-SN		195.250 €	0 €		-14,07	390.500 €	0 €		-24,02	585.750 €	0 €		-31,60
CS2-BH3-SN		195.250 €	0 €		-28,98	390.500 €	0 €		-217,31	585.750 €	0 €		180,66
CS2-BH4-SD		172.250 €	0 €		-8,73	344.500 €	0 €		-12,21	516.750 €	0 €		-14,13

Scenario	Solution Initial Capital Costs	Number of cooperative members											
		250				500				750			
		Dwellings Initial Capital Costs	Dwellings Annual Operational Costs	Solution Annual Operational Costs	Break Even Time	Dwellings Initial Capital Costs	Dwellings Annual Operational Costs	Solution Annual Operational Costs	Break Even Time	Dwellings Initial Capital Costs	Dwellings Annual Operational Costs	Solution Annual Operational Costs	Break Even Time
CS2-BH4-SC	136.750 €	6.250 €		-5,34	273.500 €	12.500 €		-6,77	410.250 €	18.750 €		-7,46	
CS2-BH5-SD	172.250 €	0 €		-8,82	344.500 €	0 €		-12,41	516.750 €	0 €		-14,39	
CS2-BH5-SC	136.750 €	6.250 €		-5,38	273.500 €	12.500 €		-6,85	410.250 €	18.750 €		-7,55	
CS2-ML1-SN	195.250 €	0 €		-13,36	390.500 €	0 €		-22,01	585.750 €	0 €		-28,19	
CS2-ML2-SN	195.250 €	0 €		-11,51	390.500 €	0 €		-17,34	585.750 €	0 €		-20,94	
CS2-ML3-SN	195.250 €	0 €		49,11	390.500 €	0 €		19,62	585.750 €	0 €		16,30	
CS2-ML4-SD	172.250 €	0 €		-8,99	344.500 €	0 €		-12,74	516.750 €	0 €		-14,85	
CS2-ML4-SC	136.750 €	6.250 €		-5,46	273.500 €	12.500 €		-6,98	410.250 €	18.750 €		-7,71	
CS2-ML5-SD	172.250 €	0 €		-14,03	344.500 €	0 €		-26,36	516.750 €	0 €		-37,56	
CS2-ML5-SC	136.750 €	6.250 €		-7,51	273.500 €	12.500 €		-10,81	410.250 €	18.750 €		-12,72	
CS2-MH1-SN	195.250 €	0 €		-33,38	390.500 €	0 €		#DIV/0!	585.750 €	0 €		98,46	
CS2-MH2-SN	195.250 €	0 €		-21,31	390.500 €	0 €		-58,20	585.750 €	0 €		-140,91	
CS2-MH3-SN	195.250 €	0 €		164,14	390.500 €	0 €		27,39	585.750 €	0 €		21,36	
CS2-MH4-SD	172.250 €	0 €		-8,63	344.500 €	0 €		-12,03	516.750 €	0 €		-13,88	
CS2-MH4-SC	136.750 €	6.250 €		-5,29	273.500 €	12.500 €		-6,70	410.250 €	18.750 €		-7,37	
CS2-MH5-SD	172.250 €	0 €		-12,54	344.500 €	0 €		-21,49	516.750 €	0 €		-28,36	
CS2-MH5-SC	136.750 €	6.250 €		-6,95	273.500 €	12.500 €		-9,68	410.250 €	18.750 €		-11,18	

Table 42. Detailed economic CBA calculations of break-even times per scenario and number of cooperative members (1000,2000,5000)

Scenario	Solution Initial Capital Costs	Number of cooperative members											
		1000				2000				5000			
		Dwellings Initial Capital Costs	Dwellings Annual Operational Costs	Solution Annual Operational Costs	Break Even Time	Dwellings Initial Capital Costs	Dwellings Annual Operational Costs	Solution Annual Operational Costs	Break Even Time	Dwellings Initial Capital Costs	Dwellings Annual Operational Costs	Solution Annual Operational Costs	Break Even Time
CS1-N1-DD	5.000 €	789.000 €	0 €	52.000 €	-52,93	1.578.000 €	0 €	92.000 €	-87,94	3.945.000 €	0 €	212.000 €	-146,30
CS1-N1-DC		647.000 €	25.000 €		-16,30	1.294.000 €	50.000 €		-19,10	3.235.000 €	125.000 €		-21,32
CS1-N2-DD		789.000 €	0 €		8,92	1.578.000 €	0 €		8,33	3.945.000 €	0 €		8,01
CS1-N2-DC		647.000 €	25.000 €		10,19	1.294.000 €	50.000 €		9,28	3.235.000 €	125.000 €		8,80
CS2-BL1-SN		781.000 €	0 €		-25,45	1.562.000 €	0 €		-31,48	3.905.000 €	0 €		-36,73
CS2-BL2-SN		781.000 €	0 €		-19,03	1.562.000 €	0 €		-22,20	3.905.000 €	0 €		-24,67
CS2-BL3-SN		781.000 €	0 €		30,00	1.562.000 €	0 €		24,33	3.905.000 €	0 €		21,84
CS2-BL4-SD		689.000 €	0 €		-17,35	1.378.000 €	0 €		-20,34	3.445.000 €	0 €		-22,70
CS2-BL4-SC		547.000 €	25.000 €		-8,49	1.094.000 €	50.000 €		-9,32	2.735.000 €	125.000 €		-9,89
CS2-BL5-SD		689.000 €	0 €		-27,92	1.378.000 €	0 €		-36,66	3.445.000 €	0 €		-45,22
CS2-BL5-SC		547.000 €	25.000 €		-11,07	1.094.000 €	50.000 €		-12,53	2.735.000 €	125.000 €		-13,61
CS2-BH1-SN		781.000 €	0 €		-134,82	1.562.000 €	0 €		4608,82	3.905.000 €	0 €		207,43
CS2-BH2-SN		781.000 €	0 €		-37,55	1.562.000 €	0 €		-52,48	3.905.000 €	0 €		-69,02
CS2-BH3-SN		781.000 €	0 €		94,02	1.562.000 €	0 €		54,56	3.905.000 €	0 €		43,54
CS2-BH4-SD		689.000 €	0 €		-15,34	1.378.000 €	0 €		-17,62	3.445.000 €	0 €		-19,36
CS2-BH4-SC		547.000 €	25.000 €		-7,86	1.094.000 €	50.000 €		-8,55	2.735.000 €	125.000 €		-9,04
CS2-BH5-SD		689.000 €	0 €		-15,65	1.378.000 €	0 €		-18,04	3.445.000 €	0 €		-19,86
CS2-BH5-SC		547.000 €	25.000 €		-7,96	1.094.000 €	50.000 €		-8,68	2.735.000 €	125.000 €		-9,17

Scenario	Solution Initial Capital Costs	Number of cooperative members											
		1000				2000				5000			
		Dwellings Initial Capital Costs	Dwellings Annual Operational Costs	Solution Annual Operational Costs	Break Even Time	Dwellings Initial Capital Costs	Dwellings Annual Operational Costs	Solution Annual Operational Costs	Break Even Time	Dwellings Initial Capital Costs	Dwellings Annual Operational Costs	Solution Annual Operational Costs	Break Even Time
CS2-ML1-SN	781.000 €	0 €		-32,83	1.562.000 €	0 €		-43,67	3.905.000 €	0 €		-54,53	
CS2-ML2-SN	781.000 €	0 €		-23,38	1.562.000 €	0 €		-28,37	3.905.000 €	0 €		-32,56	
CS2-ML3-SN	781.000 €	0 €		15,03	1.562.000 €	0 €		13,44	3.905.000 €	0 €		12,63	
CS2-ML4-SD	689.000 €	0 €		-16,20	1.378.000 €	0 €		-18,77	3.445.000 €	0 €		-20,75	
CS2-ML4-SC	547.000 €	25.000 €		-8,14	1.094.000 €	50.000 €		-8,88	2.735.000 €	125.000 €		-9,41	
CS2-ML5-SD	689.000 €	0 €		-47,80	1.378.000 €	0 €		-81,16	3.445.000 €	0 €		-140,24	
CS2-ML5-SC	547.000 €	25.000 €		-13,97	1.094.000 €	50.000 €		-16,39	2.735.000 €	125.000 €		-18,32	
CS2-MH1-SN	781.000 €	0 €		65,50	1.562.000 €	0 €		43,53	3.905.000 €	0 €		36,20	
CS2-MH2-SN	781.000 €	0 €		-494,34	1.562.000 €	0 €		177,66	3.905.000 €	0 €		97,63	
CS2-MH3-SN	781.000 €	0 €		19,23	1.562.000 €	0 €		16,71	3.905.000 €	0 €		15,49	
CS2-MH4-SD	689.000 €	0 €		-15,05	1.378.000 €	0 €		-17,24	3.445.000 €	0 €		-18,90	
CS2-MH4-SC	547.000 €	25.000 €		-7,76	1.094.000 €	50.000 €		-8,44	2.735.000 €	125.000 €		-8,91	
CS2-MH5-SD	689.000 €	0 €		-33,80	1.378.000 €	0 €		-47,59	3.445.000 €	0 €		-63,13	
CS2-MH5-SC	547.000 €	25.000 €		-12,12	1.094.000 €	50.000 €		-13,90	2.735.000 €	125.000 €		-15,25	